

MICHELE SANVICO

THE APENNINE SIBYL

A MYSTERY AND A LEGEND

SIBILLINI MOUNTAIN RANGE, A CAVE AND LAKE TO
THE OTHERWORLD¹

PART 2

3.10 Entering the Purgatory from Lough Derg

At the middle of the twelfth century, an Irish legend narrated the tale of a living man, a valiant knight named Owein, who had journeyed into a Christian Otherworld populated by ghastly demons. And that journey had been carried out not in a vision, but with his physical body, by entering a passageway set in a gloomy cave known as the 'Purgatory of St. Patrick'.

This legendary tale was related by Henry of Saltrey in his *Tractatus de Purgatorio Sancti Patricii*, in the form of a trustful account reported to him

¹ Released on February, 2nd, 3rd, 5th, 7th, 9th, 12th, 16th, 19th, 21st 2020
(http://www.italianwriter.it/TheApennineSibyl/TheApennineSibyl_Otherworld.asp)

by a monk, Gilbert of Lincoln. But, in his account, Henry of Saltrey never provides an indication on the exact whereabouts of such fateful passageway, though he says it was located in Ireland.

Fig. 79 - Ireland, Britain, Iceland and the Orkneys in a thirteenth-century miniature contained in Gerald of Wales' *Topographia Hibernica* (manuscript no. 700, National Library of Ireland, Dublin, folium 48r)

But where was the entryway to the Purgatory of St. Patrick?

Henry of Saltrey just writes «in a deserted place» («in locum desertum»), in Ireland. But where was that deserted place located?

Further information is provided by Gerald of Wales (Giraldus Cambrensis), a canon and historian who writes in the same years as Henry of Saltrey. In his *Topographia Hibernica* (*Topography of Ireland*), whose first revision was written in 1188, he included a chapter on a very special island, set in the northern region of Ireland:

«There is a lake in Ulster which contains an island divided in two parts. In one of these stands a church of especial sanctity, and it is most agreeable and delightful, as well as beyond measure glorious for the visitations of angels and the multitude of the saints who visibly frequent it. The other part, being covered with rugged crags, is reported to be the resort of devils

only, and to be almost always the theatre of which crowds of evil spirits that visibly perform their rites».

Fig. 80 - The excerpt on the island where the Purgatory of St. Patrick is located as it appears in Gerald of Wales' *Topographia Hibernica* (manuscript no. Ff.1.27, Cambridge University Library, folium 294)

[In the original Latin text: «Est lacus in partibus Ultoniae continens insulam bipartitam. Cujus pars altera, probatae religionis ecclesiam habens, spectabilis valde est et amoena; angelorum visitatione, sanctorumque loci illius visibili frequentia, incomparabiliter illustrata. Pars altera, hispida nimis et horribilis, solis daemoniis ut dicitur assignata; quae et visibilibus cacodaemonum turbis et pompis fere semper manet exposita»].

Gerald's description continues with further otherworldly details:

«This part of the island contains nine pits, and should anyone perchance venture to spend the night in one of them (which has been done, we know, at times, by some rash men), he is immediately seized by the malignant

spirits, who so severely torture him during the whole night, inflicting on him such unutterable sufferings by fire and water, and other torments of various kinds, that when morning comes scarcely any spark of life is found left in his wretched body. It is said that any one who has once submitted to these torments as a penance imposed upon him, will not afterwards undergo the pains of hell, unless he commit some sin of a deeper dye».

Fig. 81 - Pits and demonic presence on the island where the Purgatory of St. Patrick is located, from Gerald of Wales' *Topographia Hibernica* (manuscript no. Ff.1.27, Cambridge University Library, folium 294)

[In the original Latin text: «Pars ista novem in se foveas habet. In quarum aliqua si quis forte pernoctare praesumpserit, quod a temerariis hominibus nonnunquam constat esse probatum, a malignis spiritibus statim arripitur, et nocte tota tam gravibus poenis cruciatur, tot tantisque et tam ineffabilis ignis et aquae variique generis tormentis incessanter affligitur, ut mane factō vix vel minimae spiritus superstitis reliquiae misero in corpore reperiantur. Haec, ut asserut, tormenta si quis semel ex injuncta poenitentia sustinuerit, infernales amplius poenas, nisi graviora commiserit, non subibit»].

Is this the place we are looking for? Yes it is, as Gerald of Wales himself specifies:

«This place is called by the natives the Purgatory of St. Patrick».

[In the original Latin text: «Hic autem locus Purgatorium Patricii ab incolis vocatur»].

Fig. 82 - The island mentioned by Gerald of Wales and its identification with the Purgatory of St. Patrick, from *Topographia Hibernica* (manuscript no. Royal MS 13 B VIII, British Library, folium 15r)

So in the antique Irish tradition of the Purgatory of St. Patrick we have one or more hollow caves and a lake, providing an otherworldly access. A configuration that cannot but remind us of a similar configuration which is also found in Italy, in the Sibillini Mountain Range, with another Cave and another Lake, for which we suppose that some kind of legendary otherworldly access might have existed as well.

Fig. 83 - Station Island and Lough Derg, Co. Donegal, Ireland

However, from Henry of Saltrey and Gerald of Wales we still do not know the exact location of that special lake and cave in Ireland. Yet, we are about to find out that the lake's position is pinpointed by a tradition which, for more than nine hundred years, brought thousands of penitent visitors right to the gates of this Irish passageway to the Otherworld.

We are referring to Lough Derg, a lake set in County Donegal, Ireland: the traditional, historically recognised entrance to the Purgatory of St. Patrick.

3.11 St. Patrick's Purgatory as a legendary physical entryway to the afterlife

In the northern portion of Ireland, in County Donegal, there is a barren, deserted region, mostly covered with bogs, moorlands, pools and lakes, set amid desolate plateaus of low elevation, where peat and water are the main elements which are to be sensed under one's foot. Villages are scarce and the human presence is almost invisible, amid the low hills where the heath seems to have established an undisputed rule. Even today, only few roads serve this dreary, isolated territory.

From the twelfth century onwards, this far-away corner of Europe was the destination of thousands and thousands of pilgrims coming from all the countries of the continent.

They all wanted to reach Lough Derg, a small, irregularly-shaped lake some two miles long, lost in a remote corner of Ireland. They all wanted to reach the famous, legendary passageway to the Otherworld. They all wanted their dream about the afterlife, fiendish as it might be, to come true. They all wanted to enter the Purgatory of St. Patrick.

Because, in the middle of Lough Derg, two islands emerged from the waters. The first and bigger was Saints Island, on which a settlement of Augustinian friars was present.

The second island, smaller and eerie, was Station Island. There, an ancient tradition set the entrance to the Purgatory of St. Patrick, the otherworldly

region that living men were allowed to access, as described in the works by Henry of Saltrey and Gerald of Wales.

Fig. 84 - The region of the Pettigo Plateau, which overlooks Lough Derg (Co. Donegal, Ireland)

Fig. 85 - Ireland and Lough Derg (marked by the red circle) as seen from the satellite

What did pilgrims find on their arrival in Station Island? This tale is told to us, among others, by Thomas Messingham, a seventeenth-century Irish scholar who wrote a treatise on the saints of Ireland, *Florilegium insulae sanctorum seu Vitae et acta sanctorum Hiberniae*, published in 1624. In this work, the lengthy, emotional preparation rituals which the pilgrims experienced before getting into the Purgatory are described in detail:

Fig. 86 - The rituals performed by the pilgrims before entering the Purgatory of St. Patrick, from Thomas Messingham's *Florilegium insulae sanctorum seu Vitae et acta sanctorum Hiberniae* (Paris, 1624), p. 95

«For the whole time of their stay in the island, for nine days, they fasted and had only bread and water [...] During the day the pilgrim had to attend the Holy Mass thrice, in the morning, afternoon and vespers; exhausted, in the night they slept on hay or straw, without any blanket, bed nor pillow [...] Allowed to the Purgatory by the Spiritual Father who presided over the matter, they began a pilgrimage by taking off their shoes and sandals, and proceeded from the premises of the clerics into the Church dedicated to St. Patrick, making their entrance with bare feet; there they prayed, and walked for seven times a holy path within the said church [...] then they proceeded to the cross which raised in the adjoining cemetery [...] and by a trail scattered with jagged gravel they reached the lake [...] where they praised the Lord and the Angels and recited the litany of the Apostles...».

[In the original Latin text: «Toto tempore quo morantur in ipsa insula, puta per novem ipsos dies, ieiunandum erit in pane et aqua [...] Interdiu necesse habent peregrini ter obire sacras stationes, mane, meridie, vesperi; et lassii sub noctem recubant in foeno vel stramine, sine stragulo, pulvinari, culcitra [...] Admissi a Patre Spirituali qui purgatorio preest, ex instituto Canonicorum ad peregrinationem faciendam exuunt se calceos et caligas, et Ecclesiam quae Sancto Patricio inscripta est devoti nudipedes ingredientur, ibique facta oratione, sacros obeunt circuitus introrsum septies in ipso templo [...] obeunt tum crucem in caemiterio [...] in aspera et plerumque rupicola semita veniunt ad lacum [...] dum recitant orationem Dominicam, salutationem Angelicam, et symbolum Apostolorum...»].

The listed procedure was repeated for seven days in a row, with an increased commitment to the rituals on the eighth. Finally, on the ninth day, as the expectation for the imminent visit to the Purgatory was growing so intense as to become almost unbearable, the wearied, fear-oppressed pilgrims entered the conclusive stage of their spiritual preparation. The Spiritual Father admonished the pilgrims on the danger of being unclean, and reminded them of the horrors that they were about to behold, so frightful as to «overthrow the torpid, melt the stalwart, terrify the dauntless» («stupidissimus movere, rigidissimus emollire, audacissimus perterrere possint»). Then they received the remission of their sins and the Holy Communion to «protect themselves against the lords and powers of darkness» («se parent armentque contra principes et potestates tenebrarum»).

The time had finally come for them to enter the fateful cave, the earthly passageway to a ghastly Otherworld, an experience that was being announced to them as utterly harrowing and excruciating, and possibly deadly for their mortal body and immortal soul, as if it were a sort of funeral of their sinful essence:

«Here they are, those who are about to enter, sprayed with holy water before the door of the cavern, as if they were leaving to another world, [...] they can be seen moaning, sighing, [...] with groans, cries and tears, all the pilgrims now get into the cave; and, after having locked the gate from the outside, the people who had accompanied the burial leave the place».

[In the original Latin text: «Iam ingressurus, et aqua lustrali respersos in ostio speluncae, quasi in transitu ad alium orbem, [...] cernere est gementes, suspirantes, [...] cum singultu, fletu et lachrymis plerique subeunt speluncam, et accluso deforis ostio, recedunt qui comitabantur funus»].

Fig. 87 - Dread in the heart of the pilgrims just before the entrance into the Purgatory of St. Patrick, from Thomas Messingham's *Florilegium insulae sanctorum seu Vitae et acta sanctorum Hiberniae* (Paris, 1624), p. 96

Now they are in. In the Otherworld. With their physical body. At the Purgatory of St. Patrick, Lough Dergh, County Donegal, Ireland.

Not all of them will get out alive from that cave. Many will die there, amid heinous, fiendish visions.

How did the cavern present itself to the sight of the pilgrims? At the time of Thomas Messingham, in the first half of the seventeenth century, it was a hollow of limited size:

«This cavern is a small cavity made of stone, so narrow and with his vaulted roof so low that a tall man would not stand upright, nor even sit down, if not by bending his own head; in so small a space, up to nine people can be accommodated on the floor, their bodies bent over [...] the far side of the floor is covered by a great stone, under which people say is to be found that abyss and cave, which God opened to the terror of the unbelieving, while St. Patrick was praying and the ground cleaved».

[In the original Latin text: «Est autem caverna ipsa, lapidea domuncula tam angustis lateribus, et fornice tam depressa, ut homo procerae staturae adeo se erigere non posset, ut nec sedere quidem, nisi inclinata cervice valeret,

arcte se comprimunt noveni sibi assidentes et acclinantes [...] et extrema pavimenti pars substernitur grandi saxo, sub quo produnt aliqui subesse voraginem illam et foveam, quam orante Sancto, et terra dehiscente, ad terrorem obstinatorum aperuit Deus»].

Fig. 88 - The cave of St. Patrick's Purgatory in the seventeenth century, from Thomas Messingham's *Florilegium insulae sanctorum seu Vitae et acta sanctorum Hiberniae* (Paris, 1624), p. 96

This hollow, Messingham reports, was once much deeper («in prima loci institutione profundiolem fuisse»), subsequently it had been leveled («fundus speluncae complanatus fit, et reliquae terrae coaequatus») to allow people in it more easily.

Before being taken out of the cavern and brought back to the adjoining church for the closing rituals, the pilgrims were left in that hollow for 24 hours («reclusi in isto specu permanserit ieiuni 24 horas»), with no food at all and only a sip of water. A grievous seclusion so dark, so narrow, so unbearable, one's body pressed against the bodies of the other pilgrims,

gasping for air, in a limited space soon turned into a sort of burning room heated up by nine human breaths and dejections («poenosa sit reclusio tam arcta, tam obscura, tam diuturna, [...] ab intro aestuante halitu se mutuo constipantium et suffumigantium in spelunca»).

And, in addition to all that, there were visions. Visions of fiends and punishments. In the Purgatory of St. Patrick.

3.12 *The dreams at St. Patrick's Purgatory*

What did the pilgrims see during their excruciating, torturing stay in the cave set at Station Island, Lough Derg, County Donegal, Ireland? Did they see, in actual reality and with their corporeal eyes, the amazing, blood-curdling tortures depicted by Henry de Saltrey in his *Tractatus de Purgatorio Sancti Patricii*?

We can get a glimpse of what was to be seen in the Purgatory's cave from a famous excerpt written by an Italian pilgrim, Antonio Mannini from Florence, who was so bold as to venture into the hazardous journey to Lough Derg, in the year 1411:

«I thought indeed to go and return [from Dublin] in three weeks at the longest», he wrote «but through the perilous roads and other occasions we have spent three months and a half in going and returning».

[In the original Italian text: «Veramente io mi credea essere andato e tornato [da Dublino] il più lungo in tre settimane, ma per la via pericolosa per molte cagioni stemmo in andare e tornare tre mesi e mezzo»].

This passage is contained in the Codex Magliabechiano XXV, 595 (leaf 437), preserved at the Biblioteca Nazionale Centrale in Florence, and we read this remarkable text from the transcript provided by Ludovico Frati in the *Giornale storico della letteratura italiana* (Vol. III, Turin, 1886).

After his venturesome arrival in Lough Derg and Station Island, Antonio Mannini underwent the rituals which preceded the fateful entrance into the Purgatory, «with the same prayers and solemnity as is used for the dead,

neither more nor less» («con le proprie orazioni e sollemnità si fanno sopra un morto, né più né meno»). He limited the fasting to three days only, owing to the wintry weather of November. Then he was brought before the door of the Purgatory, set a few feet from the church. The canon pronounced the usual warnings and final attempts at dissuading the pilgrim from entering, saying that «many had been found dead therein [...] and they who came forth were crazed for ever after by terror» («molti s'erano trovati drento morti [...] e chi n'usciva per sempre per paura divenia smemorato»). Finally, the door was unlocked, Magini was showed into the Purgatory of St. Patrick, and the entryway was locked again behind him.

Fig. 89 - The excerpt written by Antonio Mannini on his journey to the Purgatory of St. Patrick in 1411, from the Codex Magliabechiano XXV, 595 (leaf 437), Biblioteca Nazionale Centrale, Florence (transcript by Ludovico Frati, *Giornale storico della letteratura italiana*, Vol. III, Torino, 1886, p. 156)

In utter terror, the fifteenth-century Italian visitor could notice, as we already know from the description provided by Thomas Messingham, that «the place is three feet wide, nine feet long, and high enough for a man to kneel, but not to stand upright [...] it is exactly like a sepulchre, for it is vaulted overhead» («il quale luogo è largo tre piedi e lungo nove et alto

tanto che un huomo vi puote stare ginocchione ma non dritto [...] gl'è a punto come un sepolcro, ché disopra è in volta»).

presente spari. Come fu' drento, il Calonacho serrò la porta a chiave e col medesimo battello se ne tornò all'isola della Prioria, e io nel Purgatorio serrato rimasemi; il quale luogo è largo tre piedi e lungo nove et alto tanto che un huomo vi puote stare ginocchione ma non dritto. Raxiona che gl'è a punto come un sepolcro, ché disopra è in volta ed è di verso il mezzogiorno, cioè di verso la Cappella a una tornata di tre piedi lunga là ove il Priore mi disse stessi e quivi facessi le mie orazioni e quivi m'attendessi; dove giunto, stando in orazione et in ginocchione sempre con la croce in mano, come il Priore m'avea detto, dissi i sette Salmi Penetenziali con le Letanie, e di poi dicendo una Salve Regina con 15 Ave Marie a honore delle 15 allegrezze ebbe la vergine Maria benedetta, mi ricorda con gran pianto et amarissime lagrime mi volsi con l'animo a lei per nome chiamandola come il più divotamente pote', supplicandola per me al suo diletto

Fig. 90 - Antonio Mannini is locked within the Purgatory of St. Patrick, from the Codex Magliabechiano XXV, 595 (leaf 437), Biblioteca Nazionale Centrale, Florence (transcript by Ludovico Frati, *Giornale storico della letteratura italiana*, Vol. III, Torino, 1886, p. 160)

He stayed in the Purgatory only five hours, then the canon thought it better to unlock the door and let him out to avoid death caused by icy temperature. What Mannini did see there? Here is what he himself reports:

«As I was praying I fell asleep, and whether my soul was rapt in ecstasy out of my body, or whether indeed I journeyed in my actual body, and in what way, I cannot tell you. [...] What I saw, and what was shown to me, and what I did, I may not write in a letter, nor can I utter it save in confession».

figliuolo mi dovesse aiutare alla salute dell'anima mia, e così orando m'addormentai, o se in estasi l'anima mi fu tratta dal corpo, o se pure andai col vero corpo, o come, io non te lo saprei dire; quello vidi e quello mi fu mostrato e quel feci non te lo posso scrivere per lettera, nè 'l posso dire se non in confessione; ma se mai a Dio piacerà ti riveggia, tutto per ordine ti dirò.

Fig. 91 - What Antonio Mannini beheld in the Purgatory of St. Patrick, from the Codex Magliabechiano XXV, 595 (leaf 437), Biblioteca Nazionale Centrale, Florence (transcript by Ludovico Frati, *Giornale storico della letteratura italiana*, Vol. III, Torino, 1886, p. 160)

[In the original Italian text: «Così orando m'addormentai, o se in estasi l'anima mi fu tratta dal corpo, o se pure andai col vero corpo, o come io non te lo saprei dire; quello vidi e quello mi fu mostrato e quel feci non te lo posso scrivere per lettera, né 'l posso dire se non in confessione»].

Fig. 92 - A miniature showing a bishop, demons and tormented souls from William Staunton's *Vision at St. Patrick's Purgatory* (manuscript Royal MS 17 B XLIII, British Library, London, folium 132v)

He writes nothing more. And yet we have many other witnesses, like William Staunton, an Englishman from Durham, who on 20 September 1409 had fiendish visions of men clad in white, demons and terrific

punishments, as is reported in manuscript Royal MS 17 B XLIII, preserved at the British Library in London. Others saw absolutely nothing, like the Dutch monk who entered the Purgatory at the end of the fifteenth century, and, as he had no visions at all, he complained about this before Pope Alexander VI in Rome. And the Pope issued an order for the destruction of the fake entryway to the Otherworld in 1497. The site was restored again in 1522, visited by additional thousands of pilgrims and then demolished once more in 1632 by order of the Lord Justice of Ireland, the arm of the English Crown. But that was not the Purgatory's end: the pilgrimages continued and even increased in the subsequent centuries, even though a chapel was built on the cave in 1790, in this way erasing all evidences of its former existence.

Today, the Purgatory of St. Patrick is still there, a religious and touristic site which attracts thousands of visitors every year. Of course, the cave is not accessible nor extant anymore, and contemporary visitors can only imagine what visions may have haunted the souls of their fellow-pilgrims in past centuries.

Fig. 93 - Today's entrance to the car park of the Sanctuary of St. Patrick, on the southeastern coast of Lough Derg, Co. Donegal, Ireland

However, the amazing, powerful attractiveness of the Purgatory of St. Patrick remains untouched, and people still flock to this remote Irish lake. And the reason is linked to its immense mythical might, as effectively expressed by John Drelincourt Seymour in his work *St. Patrick Purgatory - A Maedieval Pilgrimage in Ireland* (Dundalk, 1918):

«Why it was that the Purgatory at Lough Derg achieved a European reputation, and so by its brilliancy eclipsed all the other places of pilgrimage in Ireland, is a question not easy to answer; but it seems probable that what principally contributed to its favour was the belief that in 'Ultima Thule', the remotest corner of the earth, there was an actual entrance into the other world, or at all events the less pleasant regions thereof — no dream-gate of dazzling ivory through which fantasies might ascend, but a cave or grotto of stone, through which 'facilis descensus' men could wend in the body to behold sights hidden from mortal eye».

Was that true? Did a passageway to the Otherworld actually exist at that cave in Lough Derg, Ireland?

This is a fundamental issue we intend to address later in the present research paper: an issue which will prove to be of significant importance as to our investigation dedicated to the legends that inhabit the Sibillini Mountain Range, in Italy. And we will probe further into it in the following paragraphs.

4. Hot spots, crevices and landmarks: a third passageway

In the previous paragraphs, we have conducted an extensive review of the Western legendary tradition about the Otherworld and the visits carried out by human beings into the afterlife, be it in a vision or with their actual body.

We started from Odysseus and his journey to the land of the Cimmerians to perform a 'nekyia', a necromantic ritual for the summoning of the dead. Then we saw Aeneas and his visit to the Cumaean Sibyl, a travel which is both a 'nekyia' and a 'katabasis', a ghastly descent into the realm of the dead. Subsequently, we left classical antiquity and ventured into the Christian literary tradition, marked by visionary journeys carried out by

living souls in a sort of dream or divine rapture: from the *Visio Sancti Pauli Apostoli* to the *Dialogues* written by Pope St. Gregory I the Great, and then to the many medieval description which were originated in Ireland, including the *Vision of St. Adamnán* and the *Vision of Tnúgdalus*. Until we came to Henry of Saltrey's *Tractatus de Purgatorio Sancti Patricii*, which describes an actual travel carried out into the Otherworld by a living man with his actual body. And actual bodies were those of the thousands of pilgrims who, starting from the twelfth century or even earlier, reached Lough Derg, in Ireland, to cross the gate of the Purgatory of St. Patrick, in search of a physical passageway from the world of the living to the Otherworld, and of a tangible experience of the Christian afterlife.

Many other visionary tales concerning travels to the Otherworld can be retrieved in the literary traditions of classical antiquity (like the myth of Orpheus and Eurydice), early Christianity (with the apocryphal *Gospel of Nicodemus* and *Apocalypse of St. Peter*) and in the works of the Middle Ages (the *Vision of Alberic* and many others), with comprehensive collections being provided by C. S. Boswell in his *An Irish precursor of Dante* (London, 1908) and Eileen Gardiner (*Medieval Visions of Heaven and Hell: A Sourcebook*, New York, 1993). However, in the present article we listed some of the most significant visions, a bimillennial literary path that will finally lead to an undisputed apex: the artistical and theological masterwork elaborated by Dante Alighieri with his *Divine Comedy*, written in the early fourteenth century.

This is the cultural and mythical setting in which we are now going to position the legendary tales which live in the Sibillini Mountain Range, in the Italian Apennines: the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate.

In the initial part of the present research paper, we already highlighted the many clues which seem to suggest a potential legendary nature of the two sites as mythical entryways to an Otherworld: the 'test bridge' associated with the Sibyl's Cave in the account written by Antoine de la Sale; the ever-slamming doors, a contrivance typical of supernatural passageways; the Lake considered as a resting place for the body of Pontius Pilate, a sort of legendary location typically marking a passageway to Hell, the same idea being expressed by Petrus Berchorius with specific relation to the Lake. And a general presence of demons, at both the Cave and the Lake, in conjunction with the performance of necromatic rituals at either sites.

In the western-European tradition, two were the most widely known places in which the Otherworld opened its blood-curdling jaws to mortal beings. Two 'hot spots', through which living men were able to communicate with legendary, supernatural entities. Two cracks, which broke the continuity in our physical world and allowed mortal men to enter forbidden, terrific realms.

The first 'hot spot' was in Cumae, in the province of Campania, Italy. The land of the Cumaean Sibyl, who in antiquity led Aeneas to the Hades, the realm of the dead. An appalling fissure in the world of the living. A lake, Avernus, and a cave, the landmarks to the legend.

Fig. 94 - The Lake of Avernus, Cumae, Italy

The second 'hot spot' was at Lough Derg, in County Donegal, Ireland. The abode of the Purgatory of St. Patrick, which opened its gate to the horrors of Hell. Again, a crack in our physical world, the world that God created for the living. And, again, a lake and a cave. Landmarks to legend.

Fig. 95 - Lough Derg, Co. Donegal, Ireland

Was there, in the land of Europe, a third legendary entryway to the Otherworld? Did a third mythical 'hot spot' exist? Did any 'third crack' allow, somewhere and somehow, a potential link and access to the forbidden powers of the afterlife?

Fig. 96 - Lakes of Pilate, Sibillini Mountain Range, Italy

Yes, there was a third entrance. A third direful, ominous 'hot spot'. A crevice in the continuum of mortal life. And, once more, it was a lake and a cave. The Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilatus. Two further legendary landmarks. In the Italian Apennines.

Fig. 97 - Three legendary entryways to the Otherworld: St. Patrick's Purgatory, Cumae and the Sibillini Mountain Range

This is the assumption we are trying to explore in the present research paper: according to an antique, almost forgotten tradition, the Sibillini Mountain Range was possibly considered as a third fateful passageway to realms that are normally forbidden to living men.

And in the next paragraphs we will further unfold the potential legendary process that, according to our assumption, might have led to this mythical vision.

4.1 Geographical landmarks: *Cumae, a physical entryway to legend*

In the land of Italy, south of Rome, the former capital of a vanished empire, along the coastline of the Tyrrhenian Sea, we find a territory which was qualified in antiquity as 'Felix', the fertile region: it is Campania.

Campania, the region of Naples, or antique 'Parthenope', a colony founded in the eighth century B.C. by Greek settlers, who had also established a colony in Cumae, ten miles to the west.

As we wrote in our article *A Sibyl called Cimmerian: exploring the potential link to the Apennine Sibyl*, this was, and still is, a territory «which is heavily, permanently marked by the mightiest subterranean powers in Europe. A land blessed - and doomed - by the Gods of the Netherworld».

Fig. 98 - The territory of Cumae in today's province of Campania (Italy), a picture we already presented in our paper *A Sibyl called Cimmerian: exploring the potential link to the Apennine Sibyl*

For it is in Campania that one of the most dangerous active volcanoes in the world raises its broken ridges: Vesuvius, the mountain that unleashed death and destruction over the Roman cities of Pompeii and Herculaneum in 79 A.D. And this is also in Campania, eastward of Cumae and Cape Misenus, that «since time immemorial, the ground has been ravaged by the

fury of volcanoes». There lies «the most renowned Phlegraean Fields, a large volcanic area hiding one of the most dangerous, and still active today, subterranean magmatic chambers in the world».

A number of volcanic calderas (Mount Barbaro, the large Astroni crater, and many others) are present in this relatively small area, including the pocket-size yet impressive Monte Nuovo ('The New Mountain'), a tiny volcano which was created from nothing by a sudden eruption which took place between September, 29 and October, 6 1538. Earthquakes, emission of volcanic gases and measurable displacements of the ground (a phenomenon known as 'bradyseism') have always happened there.

And here also lies a lake, once mysterious and inaccessible. Its name is Lake Avernus.

Fig. 99 - Lake Avernus with Aeneas and the Cumaean Sybil in a early nineteenth-century painting by Joseph Mallord William Turner (Tate Gallery, London)

«Avernus, entirely encircled by ridges above, looming on it from every side but at a single gap; [...] in old times it was enshrouded by an inaccessible wood made of huge trees, which covered with gloomy, superstitious shade the whole lake».

[In a 1571 Latin translation of the original text in Greek: «Avernus superciliis recta sursum enatis et undique praterquam in aditu imminentibus [...]; olim enim sylva inaccessa magnarum arborum obsita, ob superstitionem ipsum sinum obumbrabant»].

These words were written by Strabo, the Greek geographer and historian, in his first-century work *Geographica*, a quote we already presented in the initial part of the present paper. Avernus, in antiquity a lake of darkness and death: «the birds that cross the lake», Strabo reports, «fall down into the waters, being killed by the vapours that rise from it, as it happens for places which are linked to the Netherworld» («aves quae supervolarent in aquam decidere, exanimatas aeris exhalatione, quemadmodum i Plutonijs locis fit» in Latin).

In this very place Publius Vergilius Maro, in Book VI of his *Aeneid*, written in the first century B.C., set the entryway to the House of Hades, the Otherworld of classical antiquity:

Fig. 100 - The passages on the Lake Avernus and the cave to the Otherworld from Vergil's *Aeneid* as it appears in ninth-century manuscript Latin 7926 (Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Département des Manuscrits, folia 125v and 126r)

«Then [...] they reached the foul jaws of stinking Avernus [...] There was a deep stony cave, huge and gaping wide, sheltered by a dark lake and shadowy woods, [...] that the Greeks called it by the name Avernus».

[In the original Latin text (v. 201, 237-238 and 242):
«Inde ubi venere ad fauces grave olentis Averni [...] Spelunca alta fuit vastoque immanis hiatu, scrupea, tuta lacu nigro nemorumque tenebris, [...] unde locum Grai dixerunt nomine Aornon»].

And, since ages rooted in the most ancient myths, this lake has always been the most suitable place to stage ghastly encounters with the Otherworld. Indeed a classical tradition set in this very place the most famous 'nekyia' performed by Odysseus in Book XI of Homer's *Odyssey*, as Strabo himself narrates:

«Those who lived prior to our age applied to Lake Avernus the fairy tale about necromancy which is found in Homer, and so much so that they thought here was the oracle where the dead uttered prophecies as if they were alive: the oracle to which Ulysses came».

[In the Latin translation from the original Greek text: «Qui nos aetate antecesserunt, Necyae Homericæ fabulas Averno applicaverunt, atque adeo narrant fuisse ibi oraculum ubi vita defuncti responsa darent, eoque Ulissem advenisse»].

«The path to hell is easy - Black Pluto's door is open night and day» (in the original Latin text, v.126-127: «facilis descensus Averno - noctes atque dies patet atri ianua Ditis»). So speaks the Cumaean Sibyl, the gatekeeper who guards the fateful passageway at Lake Avernus, in the name of divine Hecate, goddess of witchcraft and necromancy.

For Lake Avernus is nothing less than a volcanic crater lake, an eerie manifestation of chthonian powers in itself.

It is of great interest to remark that, by the Lake Avernus, in past centuries many hollows could be found, and they were marked by significant, eerie features, as noted by Giuseppe Mormile in his *Descrittione dell'amenissimo distretto della citta di Napoli (A description of the most pleasant district of the town of Naples)*, dating to 1617:

«On accessing the Lake Avernus from the side that looks to the west, through a small and impractical passage on the left, you descend into the

Cavern, which is known by the local people as the Sibyl's cave [...] but now it has been walled up, because many people who ventured in it lost their lives out of the fumes and vapors. [...] In the area of Cumae a huge cave is found [...] this cave is ruined at many spots because of the rainfalls, so that the exhalations cannot escape because all holes are closed and the hollows are filled up with mephitic vapors; those who enter endanger their own life, as it happened to many foolish men who were so bold as to get in, out of curiosity, and fell dead owing to the corrupted air; and the same happened to ignorant people [...] they dream that in these caverns many hidden treasures may lie, so they boldly venture into the hollows, and then are found dead there, as they are seized by the Fiend, who deceives the men who believe in him by such guiles».

Fig. 101 - The excerpts on the hazardous hollows in the territory of Cumae as described in Giuseppe Mormile's *Descrizione dell'amenissimo distretto della città di Napoli* (Naples, 1617, p. 132-133 and 175-176)

[In the original Italian text: «Nell'entrar del Lago Averno nella parte che guarda l'Occidente, per una picciola e malageuole entrata a man sinistra, che giù ti conduce si discende alla Grotta, che volgarmente chiamano della Sibilla [...] ma hora è murata, poiché all'andare innanzi per le cattive essalationi, molti vi lasciavano la vita. [...] Dentro il distretto di Cuma è una grotta grande [...] è questa grotta in molte parti della terra soffocata per causa delle piggie, e così non potendo l'essalationi salir in alto per rispetto che trouano l'uscite soffocate riempiono dette caverne, e si corrompono in

modo c' chi v'entra, v' a manifesto periglio della vita, il che è avvenuto a molti huomini pazzi, che per voler entrare, s'era vero la cosa, vi si sono rimasti morti dalla corruttione dell'aria, et gli ignoranti [...] credono che in dette caverne vi siano grandissimi tesori nascosti, e con pertinacia v'entrano, onde ispeso vi rimangono morti, e divengono preda del Demonio, che con tali lusinghe inganna chi a lui crede»].

Volcanoes, exhalations, dark and unfathomable waters, displacements and tremors. The breath of the Earth, which manifests its mighty presence to the terror-stricken gaze of mortal men. And, since time immemorial, the dreams of men, imaginative visions of subterranean realms of deities and nightmares of a gloomy life after earthly life, began to attach to this dreadful site.

The Lake Avernus and a dark cavern laying nearby: two geographical landmarks which, from mere natural features as they were, by the frightened souls of men were turned into a passageway to the Otherworld. A crack in the continuity of our everyday world, the abode of mortals, providing an access to the divine, the eternal, and the cursed.

A legendary 'hot spot', whose points of reference were a lake and a cave, which acted as landmarks with their intrinsic, natural, physical ability to attract myths.

This legendary transformation into a 'hot spot' occurred possibly since the earliest antiquity, as a result of the physical peculiarities of such wondrous place: peculiarities which rendered it able to generate a powerful mythical attraction for highly-emotional legendary narratives. Life and death, bodily existence and afterlife, mortality and divinity: the basical hopes and terrors which are housed in the hearts of men and women found a most fit abode at this small portion of Italy and Europe.

Attraction of myths, generation of legends in connection to specific geographical locations. Our reader may remember that this is a topic we have always been considering as a main issue throughout the investigation we are conducting on the Sibillini Mountain Range and its legendary heritage.

In the case of Cumae, we can easily discern the attractive pull which directs to that specific spot such powerful myths as the journeys of Aeneas and Odysseus to the gates of the Otherworld. It is the volcanic nature of the land, made of small lakes, caves, vapors and perennial vibrations of the ground: a theatrical set which is absolutely fit to host terrifying narratives about subterranean afterworlds inhabited by the dead.

So Lake Avernus and a cave lying in its proximity (today extant anymore, owing to the ceaseless commotions of the earth which have been affecting the place for millennia) rendered Cumae one of the well-established, illustrious, celebrated 'hot spots' in Europe through which a mythical access to the Otherworld was allowed to mortal men.

A crack. A fissure. A crevice pierced in our normal world, a ghastly break drilled in all rational, reassuring beliefs held by men in their hearts.

And the landmark, the distinctive emblem is a lake and a cave.

Fig. 102 - Lake Avernus from Giuseppe Mormile's *Descrizione dell'amenissimo distretto della città di Napoli* (Naples, 1617, p. 128)

These landmarks will also affect the legendary tale which live amid the Sibillini Mountain Range, as we will see in the next paragraph.

4.2 A mythical resonance between Cumae and the central Apennines

Can we detect any relationship between the legend of the Cumaean Sibyl, with her Lake Avernus and cave to Hades, in Cumae, and the tale of an Apennine Sibyl, with another Lake and Cave and a possible entryway to an Otherworld set amid the Sibillini Mountain Range?

Yes, a relation does exist, as attested by the many literary witnesses we are going to retrace in the present paragraph. But the two legendary tales are substantially independent and unrelated: no antique tradition has ever provided any link between the two Sibyls and their respective legendary tales, as we fully demonstrated in our previous articles *A Sibyl called Cimmerian: exploring the potential link to the Apennine Sibyl* and *The Apennine Sibyl: a journey into history in search of the oracle*.

Their mutual relation is far more subtle. It is an indirect relationship. A link which is based on mythical resonances, fostered by a number of similarities - a lake, a cave, an otherworldly gateway - which the two legends manifestly present when their respective tales are told to audiences. Across the centuries, this resulted in a transfer of narrative themes from Cumae to the Sibillini Mountain Range.

Let's try to retrace this fascinating process of storytelling. An oral process which has been developing itself for centuries and centuries, possibly since Roman times.

Since classical antiquity, a lake and a cave in Cumae, Italy, had been a known landmark, a geographical feature which was reputed to signal the presence of a legendary 'hot spot': a crack pierced in our physical, ordinary world, through which an entrance to a mythical Otherworld was provided, namely the House of Hades depicted by Publius Vergilius Maro in his *Aeneid*.

But another Cave and another Lake existed. In the elevated fastnesses of what we know today as the Sibillini Mountain Range, in central Italy, there was a glacial cirque encircled by precipitous cliffs, with still, icy waters at its bottom. A few miles away, in the same mountains and in full line of sight, a cavern opened its jaws of darkness on the peak of a crowned mount.

Fig. 103 - The Lakes of Pilate in the Sibillini Mountain Range

Since time immemorial, the two geographical landmarks were nested amid the craggy peaks of the Italian Apennines, in the central portion of the peninsula. And they, too, were the subject of some kind of legendary tale.

What was that tale? In our previous articles *Birth of a Sibyl: the medieval connection* and *A legend for a Roman prefect: the Lakes of Pontius Pilate*, we fully demonstrated that the legendary narratives concerning a hidden realm of a sensual Sibyl and a burial place for Pontius Pilate were extraneous tales whose origin lies elsewhere. The clues to the real, original legend inhabiting the central Apennines are retraced in another article, *Sibillini Mountain Range: the legend before the legends*: in it, we saw that

both sites in the Sibillini Mountain Range seem to share some common aspects. Both the Lake and the Cave saw necromantic rituals being performed at either sites; they both are described as inhabited by some sort of fiendish presences; they are both linked to devastation of the neighbouring land arising from necromancy effected there. In addition to that, in the first section of the present paper we showed that both sites seem to be marked by a number of features which are typically associated to literary narratives concerning passageways to the Otherworld, including a 'test bridge', magical ever-slamming doors, and straight references to Hell and its inhabitants.

Fig. 104 - Mount Sibyl in the Sibillini Mountain Range

The Lake's and Cave's original tale, which still we do not know in detail, was never registered on manuscripts, though we find many marks of it in the literary witnesses, dating back to the fourteenth century at the earliest, that describe the two legendary sites in central Italy.

Nonetheless, one specific fact is undisputable: though unregistered in writing, the legendary tale on the Lake and Cave set in the central Apennines has been circulating for centuries and centuries, possibly since the age of ancient Rome, and was being told amid local peasants, wayfarers, storytellers, and men of letters. Later literary witnesses are only the re-surfacing, traceable emergences of some sort of earlier oral tradition, which was known and was attached to the two landmarks hidden amid the

Apennines since time immemorial. Two landmarks which had existed there for thousands and thousands of years.

In this framework, which goes from classical antiquity to the Middle Ages, we can presume that the Lake and Cave, set in the Italian Apennines, were already at the center of some kind of emotional attention in the centuries which precede the fourteenth, in connection to features and characters which we know that are often connected to the legendary narratives concerning mythical entryways to the Otherworld.

But, during the centuries of late antiquity and the early Middle Ages, any oral tale that may have been circulating about a Lake, a Cave, and a possible passageway to the Otherworld set in the central Apennines would definitely have undergone an immediate association with the antique, utterly famous, thoroughly illustrious, most-widely known narrative about Cumae, the Lake Avernus and the entryway to the Hades, as contained in Publius Vergilius Maro's *Aeneid*.

Fig. 105 - Lake Avernus at Cumae

Any oral storyteller confronting with the eerie story of an otherworldly Lake and Cave lost in the middle of the Apennines would have obtained a most natural and common reply from the people who happened to listen to such legendary account: «This tale reminds us of Cumae, Lake Avernus and the Hades».

So a most natural and straightforward process must have taken place: a contamination and partial mix-up between the two narratives and sites: the lake and cave by Cumae, and a Lake and Cave hidden amid a mountain chain in central Italy.

The landmarks set in the Apennines could not but attract, in a sort of predictable process, the classical aura and suggestions linked to the realm of the Cumaean Sibyl: a classical tale that seems to peculiarly fit this further legendary setting made up by another lake and another cave, though located in a different area, out of the patent similarities that can be easily noticed by any audience.

In this legendary framework, the mythical tale based in Cumae must have undergone a sort of migration, partially copying itself into the Sibillini Mountain Range, as oral storytellers proceeded to combine the new tale with aspects drawn from the more ancient and illustrious narrative. And, as a side effect arising from this process, the less eminent narrative concerning the two sites set in central Italy certainly earned more credibility and strength from the contribution offered by the classical legend: if in Roman times a lake and cave already used to pinpoint an entryway to the Otherworld, why shouldn't it be assumed that a further passageway existed, especially when marked by another couple of similar landmarks, again a Lake and Cave?

So, an original tale related to an otherworldly passageway set in the Apennines received narrative support and additional features from the antique legend of Cumae, even though the Cumaean Sibyl had nothing to do with the Lake and Cave in the Apennines, nor any classical source has ever attested any connection of the Cumaean to the Apennines, as fully illustrated in our previous papers *A Sibyl called Cimmerian: exploring the potential link to the Apennine Sibyl* and *The Apennine Sibyl: a journey into history in search of the oracle*.

It is the otherworldly site set in the Apennines, featuring a Lake and a Cave, which attracts a few references to the Cumaean Sibyl, equally provided with her own lake and cave in Cumae.

So a Sibyl begins to inhabit the cliffs of the Apennines: but this Sibyl is just a sort of copy of the traditional character of the Cumaean oracle, who is

transplanted into central Italy following a pull that is only induced by mutual, manifold similarities, both physical and legendary, which can manifestly be perceived between the two locations. In actual tradition, the original legend of the Cumaean Sibyl has no roots of any sort amid the Apennines.

Fig. 106 - Aeneas and the Cumaean Sibyl, on their way through the Hades set beneath the Lake Avernus, meet the three-headed dog Cerberus in Vergil's *Aeneid* (manuscript Vat Lat 3225, Vatican Apostolic Library, folium 48v)

This process is fully visible in the work *Guerrino the Wretch*, written by Andrea da Barberino at the beginning of the fifteenth century. In this romance, it is the Apennine Sibyl herself, endowed with oracular powers as the Cumaean prophetess, who proclaims her identification with the Cumaean Sibyl in front of the valiant knight Guerrino:

«I want you to know my name. I was called 'Cumaean' by the Romans for I was born in a town in the countryside whose name is Cumae: before I was sentenced to this place I lived in the world one thousand two hundred years. When Aeneas came to Italy, I led him through Hell: and I was seven hundred years old at that time».

[In the original Italian text: «Io volgio che tu Sapia el mio nome. Io fui chiamata da Romani chumana perche io naqui in una Città di champagna

chiamata cumana: e stieti al mondo prima ch'io fussi iudichatta qui mille ducento anni, in po' ché quando enea vene intalia, io lo menai per tuto lo Inferno, et allora io aveva Setecento anni»].

Fig. 107 - The Apennine Sibyl calls herself «Cumaeon» in Andrea da Barberino's romance *Guerrino the Wretch* (manuscript no. MA297, Biblioteca Civica “Angelo Mai”, Bergamo, folia 138v and 139r)

And this legendary link to the Cumaean Sibyl remains visible through the subsequent centuries. Less than a hundred years later, the Cumaean origin of the Apennine Sibyl is mentioned by Ludovico Ariosto as well, with the following words included in his poem *Orlando Furioso*: «[...] the Cumæan Sibyl [...] who fled, in antiquity, to a Cavern in the territory of Norcia, placed on a mountain-top amidst a gloomy forest, from the charming abode she used to live in at earlier times» (in the original Italian text: «la Sibilla Cumea, la qual ridotta / s'era in quei tempi a la Nursina grotta / su gli aspri monti in una selva folta / da i luoghi ameni, ove habitava prima»). And a further statement of the same sort, connecting Cumae and Norcia, is provided in Canto XXXIII:

«The room that I mentioned in a preceding 'Canto',
Merlin with his spellbook, be it at the Lake Avernus,
or at the caves by Norcia,
he ordered the demons to build in one single night».

[In the original Italian text: «La sala ch'io dicea ne l'altro canto, Merlin col libro, o fosse al lago Averno, o fosse sacro alle Nursine grotte, fece far dai demonii in una notte»].

Fig. 108 - The passages contained in Ludovico Ariosto's *Orlando Furioso* on the new abode of the Cumaean Sibyl, from the 'additional stanzas', and the magical power of both the Lake Avernus and the caves in Norcia, from Chapter XXXIII (from an edition printed in Lyon, France, in 1556, p. 502 and 307)

However no ancient source ever reports the news of such a transfer of a classical Sibyl from Cumae to the Sibillini Mountain Range, out of an alleged conviction or sentence. The two Sibyls are basically unrelated and independent, as they are linked together only by a transfer of narratives fostered by a number of similar traits that mark both Cumae and the Sibillini Mountain Range, either site being provided with a lake and a cave, in an otherworldly narrative setting.

After this initial contamination phase between Cumae and the Apennines, a further overlay process begins and strengthens during the centuries of the High Middle Ages.

As we already demonstrated in our previous paper *Birth of a Sibyl: the medieval connection*, with the increasing diffusion of the Matter of Britain and the Arthurian cycle throughout Europe, the local Apennine myth attracted a number of narrative features connected to Morgan le Fay and

her necromantic companion Sebile, a northern-European elaboration connected, in turn, to classical Sibyls through the mediation of an oral tradition which can be traced in *Erec*, a poem written by Hartmann von Aue in the twelfth century. Following the success and widespread acceptance of the literary themes proposed within the Matter of Britain, the Sibyl of the Apennines became fully marked by a number of features which pertain to the enchantress Morgan/Sebile, including a magically hidden court, a proclivity to imprison brave knights, and a peculiar lasciviousness. All marks that the Cumaen Sibyl has never known.

Thus, the lineage of the Apennine Sibyl, as portrayed in the literature of the fifteenth century, is to be traced back not to the Cumaean Sibyl, but to the character of Morgan/Sebile, which belongs to a different tradition and has but indirect links to classical Sibyls.

Only one aspect will the Apennine Sibyl retain of her Cumaean counterpart: the oracular powers, the ability to utter prophecies, a gift to which Guerrino will resort with a view to unveil his own unknown origin and parents.

So, we can conclusively suppose that the relationship between our Sibyl of the Apennines and the Cumaean did not originate from any direct connection between the two legendary tales, and was fostered instead by a mutual resemblance and affinity which manifestly marked the two sites: a mysterious lake at both places, both with a dark cavern nearby, and both allowing a passageway to the Otherworld, be it the classical House of Hades at Cumae or another sort of chthonian afterlife hidden beneath the central Apennines.

This mutual resemblance was so strong and appealing that it also worked the other way round: from a chivalric realm of lecherous delights, like the Sibyl's Cave set amid the Sibillini Mountain Range, to a similar, illusory realm that some gullible northern-European visitors were seeking in the area of Cumae, with a further mix-up involving the two legendary accounts. This is found in *De Schismate*, a work written in 1410 by Theodericus aus Nieheim (Dietrich of Niem), a German historian and member of the papal court in Rome:

«Furthermore, four miles away [from Baiæ] Mount St. Barbara raises on a plain, round and imposing, which many deluded Germans name as 'The Grail', claiming that, as many report in that region, in it many men live and will be living until the Day of Judgment, who revel in pleasures and delights, as they are endlessly seized by fiendish lasciviousness».

[In the original Latin text: «Et deinde ad quatuor miliaria prope cernitur mons sanctae Barbarae in plano campo, eminens et rotundus, quem delusi multi Alemani in vulgari appellant der Gral, asserentes, prout etiam in illis regionibus plerique autumant, quod in illo multi sunt homines vivi et victuri usque ad diem iudicii, qui tripudiis et deliciis sunt dediti, et ludibriis diabolicis perpetuo irretiti»].

Fig. 109 - The excerpt on a demonic realm of bliss concealed near Cumae as it appears in Theodericus aus Nieheim's *De Schismate Universali* (from an edition printed in Strasbourg in 1609, Book II, Chapter XX, p. 99)

This «mons sanctae Barbarae» is Mount Barbaro, the volcanic cone which overlooks Cumae and the Lake Avernus, the setting which traditionally belongs to the classical Cumaean Sibyl, who never inhabited any hidden, unchaste court: this setting magnetized the northern-European tale of the

fairy kingdom of eternal bliss, a narrative connected to Morgan/Sebile, utterly foreign to Cumae, but which had established firmer and more successful roots amid the Sibillini Mountain Range.

So a strong narrative relationship between Cumae and the Sibillini Mountain Range existed, owing to the presence of similar geographical features, a lake and a cave, and out of a common otherworldly character that marked both sites.

When was this connection born? The answer is not known. The link between the legendary tales which inhabited the two sites was established in a past that now we cannot trace, in the absence of classical and late-antiquity literary witnesses, and across the undetectable, subterranean flows of oral narratives and unwritten storytelling which circulated amid popular and aristocratic audiences.

And we also have a sort of 'smoking gun' which points exactly in this same direction: a transplant of themes and topics from Cumae to the Sibillini Mountain Range.

Fig. 110 - The Lakes set in the Sibillini Mountain Range named after Lake Avernus in the sixteenth-century diagram found in manuscript Vat Lat 5241 (Vatican Apostolic Library, folium 9v)

As a matter of fact, the mythical connection between the tale which was centered at Cumae and the legend that lived amid the Apennines is further attested in a Vatican manuscript, which we already mentioned in a previous paragraph. In it, we find a striking drawing, which dates back to the middle of the sixteenth century and depicts a journey through the territory of the central Apennines, in search of the eerie Cave and Lake. But the latter is not labelled as 'Pilate's'. The indication set down by the unknown draftsman is very clear: this is «the Lake of Avernus of Norcia» (in the original Italian text: «il laco averno di Norcia»).

There is only one 'Lake Avernus' in Italy, and it is the one by Cumae. Nonetheless, the mythical affinity between the two legends was so strong that the name of the lake quoted in Vergil's *Aeneid*, a geographical landmark to the Otherworld, was transferred amid the Apennines, and attached to our demonic Lake.

And in the present article we want to add another potential transfer of themes and literary images from the Cumaean Hades, as described in the *Aeneid*, to the Sibyl's Cave as portrayed by Antoine de la Sale, a transfer we did not mention in our previous paper *The literary truth about the magical doors in 'The Paradise of Queen Sibyl'*. In that paper, we analysed the origin of the ever-slamming metal doors, the legendary device included by the fifteenth-century French author in his description of the enchanted realm of the Apennine Sibyl:

Fig. 111 - The ever-slamming metal doors which are found within the Sibyl's Cave according to Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 11r)

«... within that cave, up to the metal doors, which slam ceaselessly day and night, opening wide and then shutting close again [...] in the cavern, there are two doors made of metal, slamming day and night without rest...».

[In the original French text: «... dedans ceste cave, jusques es portes de metall, qui jour et nuyt et sans ceser battent, cloant et ouvrant [...] à l'endroit de la cave, sont les deux portes de metal, qui jour et nuyt batent sans cesser...»].

We saw that the ever-slamming metal devices are typical otherworldly contrivances, a point of passage which opens its threatening jaws to test the souls for the admission into enchanted or otherworldly regions, with an illustrious ancestor to be traced back to the magical gates of the Symplegades, the clashing rocks of the Argonauts. However, we lacked a strong explanation for the recurrent metallic nature of such otherworldly gates and lashing devices, an explanation we can now retrieve in the visionary, appalling image that Publius Vergilius Maro provides in Book VI of his *Aeneid*, in which he describes the frightful gates of the Tartarus, the abyss of sentenced sinners, guarded by a Fury, Tisiphone (vv. 552-556 and 570-573):

«A gate fronts it, vast, with adamantine pillars,
that no human force, not the heavenly gods themselves,
can overturn by war: an iron tower rises into the air,
and seated before it, Tisiphone, clothed in a blood-wet dress,
keeps guard of the doorway, sleeplessly, night and day [...]
Tisiphone the avenger, armed with her whip, without rest lashes and hits
the guilty sinners,
and threatening them with the fierce
snakes in her left hand [...]
Then at last the accursed doors open, screeching on jarring hinges».

[In the original Latin text:

«Porta adversa ingens, solidoque adamante columnae,
vis ut nulla virum, non ipsi excindere bello
caelicolae valeant; stat ferrea turris ad auras,
Tisiphoneque sedens, palla succincta cruenta,
vestibulum exsomnis servat noctesque diesque, [...]
Continuo sontes ultrix accincta flagello
Tisiphone quatit insultans, torvosque sinistra
intentans angues[...].
Tum demum horrisono stridentes cardine sacrae

panduntur portae»].

Fig. 112 - The iron tower of the gates of Tartarus from Publius Vergilius Maro's *Aeneid* (manuscript Vat Lat 3225, Vatican Apostolic Library, folium 50v)

Again, we retrieve a metal gate and an ever-lashing contrivance, a powerful image typically belonging to otherworldly narratives since classical antiquity, in the context of an account which concerns the Apennine Sibyl and the Sibillini Mountain Range, with a clear, illustrious lineage that can be traced in the past back to an eminent legendary tale connected with Cumae, its Sibyl and the passage to an ancient Otherworld, the House of Hades, with its inner pit, the Tartarus.

Following the above considerations, which we set down in the present research and in a number of preceding articles, we believe that the keyword to the legendary tale of the Sibillini Mountain Range is Otherworld. An Otherworld that men believed they could access from a passageway connected to a Lake and Cave set amid the blood-curdling, precipitous cliffs of the Apennines. And when this story was narrated before audiences, a similar narrative used to come to mind: Cumae, its lake and cave, its Hades, and its Sibyl.

No Cumaean Sibyl has ever inhabited the Sibillini Mountain Range. All references to the Cumaean oracle as found in the legendary tale of the Apennine Sibyl are the product of a transfer of narrative themes from Cumae, with its lake and cave and otherworldly entryway, to the central Apennines, with another Lake, another Lake, and, as many clues seem to indicate, another passageway to some sort of Otherworld. All that was additionally masked by a further legendary layer of northern-European origin, which featured a lascivious Sibyl/Sebile/Morgan who used to

imprison brave knights in a magical, concealed realm, in endless, sinful bliss.

Is that all? No. This story is still more complex than that. There is a further point we intend to stress.

Because Cumae was not the one and only affinity that existed between the Apennine legend and an otherworldly myth. Another contamination between different tales occurred in the High Middle Ages.

It was, again, a lake and a cave. It was, once more, an Otherworld.

It was the Purgatory of St. Patrick.

4.3 Geographical landmarks: St. Patrick's Purgatory, a further physical passageway to myth

After having returned to Cumae, its Lake Avernus and the cave through which mortals could access the afterworld of classical antiquity, let's go back to Ireland once again and summarise the physical and geographical characters of Lough Derg, the lake which housed a small island and a hollow that provided an entryway to the so-called Purgatory of St. Patrick.

As we already saw in a previous chapter within this same research paper, Lough Dergh is a small lake lying in County Donegal, part of the province of Ulster, Ireland, set in a desolate region amid low hills and plateaus. Water and peat are the main elements present in the area, covered with moors and only sparsely inhabited. In past centuries, a journey to Lough Derg was a daring and uncomfortable accomplishment, and, apart from the Purgatory of St. Patrick, there would have been no reason to venture oneself into a journey to so remote and far-off a place.

A lake and a cave: again, two geographical landmarks, which for some reason are turned into a passageway to the Otherworld. Like in Cumae, here we find another dreadful crack in our ordinary world, a point of access towards a realm which does not belong to living men.

Fig. 113 - An aerial vision of Station Island, Lough Derg, Co. Donegal, Ireland

Many lakes are found in this same area. But only Lough Derg became the very special lake which had a Purgatory in it, a legendary 'hot spot' manifesting itself on the surface of Earth. And the question is: why?

Why did the fears of men for a fiendish afterlife, deeply set in the heart of the people of the Middle Ages, happen to materialise at this specific point of Ireland?

Lough Derg also has many islands in it. However, only one of them, the so-called 'Station Island', was at the center of a long-lasting attention throughout Europe. Again, why? Scholars believe that the word 'station' may indicate an ancient military outpost, a 'statio' in Latin; yet this is not enough to provide any clue as to the reason for the positioning of a physical passageway to the afterlife within that specific islet.

The point we intend to highlight is that a very specific place, in our physical world, namely Lough Derg and its cave in Ireland, had the power to generate, or attract, a potent legend of this sort. And the reason is possibly connected to the very nature of that place.

Fig. 114 - Station Island in the seventeenth century from a map contained in James Ware's *De Hibernia et antiquitatibus ejus, disquisitiones* (London, 1654, p. 191)

An attraction process that we already found at work at Cumae, with the volcanic nature of its territory, and we will find it at work - as we will later see - in the Sibillini Mountain Range, too.

So how could Station Island attract such a myth? As it happened for Cumae, and as we assumed in the case of the Sibillini Mountain Range (see our previous articles on the origin of the legends of the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate), it actually appears that the legend of a Purgatory of St. Patrick must have arisen from some odd condensation of a peculiar nature which marks this place, the cave at Lough Derg.

Henry of Saltrey calls it a «fossam rotundam», a round hollow in the ground; Gerald of Wales uses the word «foveas», which means pits or caverns; Thomas Messingham reports about a «caverna», a cave; Giovanni

Mannini portrays a place as narrow as a «sepulchre»; Froissart reports that the hollow is a sort of «cellier», a cellar. James Ware, in his *De Hibernia et antiquitatibus ejus, disquisitiones*, provides the following detailed description as to the situation of the Purgatory to be found in 1654:

«As to the Cave itself, it is cut out of the rock, covered with broad stones at the top and green turf over them. When the door is shut, it is lighted only with one little window in a rounded corner. The space between the walls is 16 feet and a half, and the width is two feet [...] The cave is very small, and so is the Island».

[In the original Latin text: «Ad Antrum ipsum quod attinet, E saxo vivo constructum est, saxisque latis obtectum, cum terra superimposita gramine vestita. Clauso ostio, lucem aliquam præbet unica fenestella, in angulo recurvatis. Continet in longitudine intra muros 16 pedes et dimidium, in latitudine plerumque duos [...] Atque ut specus est exigua, ita etiam et Insula»].

Fig. 115 - The excerpt on the entryway to St. Patrick's Purgatory from James Ware's *De Hibernia et antiquitatibus ejus, disquisitiones* (London, 1654, p. 192)

How did it happen that a small, insignificant cave of Ireland, lost in a tiny island set in the middle of a remote lake amid the most uninviting moorlands, aroused the dreams of men and their yearning for a glimpse of

the afterlife? What peculiar condensation arising from the very nature of the place did attract a legend so appalling and emotional?

Scholars have not yet spotted the exact reason for such an amazing renown. However, we may get a clue on what this peculiar condensation might be when we read a few particular lines drawn from Thomas Messingham's *Florilegium insulae sanctorum seu Vitae et acta sanctorum Hiberniae*, published in 1624, from which we already quoted. According to Messingham, who in turn quotes from David Rothe, an Irish bishop, during their stay in Station Island the pilgrims underwent a harsh weakening process which brought them on the brink of sheer starvation:

Fig. 116 - Lack of food and exhaustion being experienced by the pilgrims before their entrance into the Purgatory of St. Patrick, from Thomas Messingham's *Florilegium insulae sanctorum seu Vitae et acta sanctorum Hiberniae* (Paris, 1624), p. 95

«For all the time of their stay in the said island, that is for nine days, they fasted and ate only bread and water, yet not according to their wish, but with one single meal including unleavened bread cooked beneath the ashes or on a grill; or an uncooked oat flour mixed with the lake's water, or cooked or seldom boiled in a cauldron, with neither salt in it nor any other seasoning; and all such raw and scarce food, though disturbing for their bowels, was made available only rarely during the space of a full day; they likewise were not allowed to allay their thirst when they needed water for their parched mouths».

[In the original Latin text: «Toto tem[po]re quo morantur in ipsa insula, puta per novem ipsos dies, ieiunandum erit in pane et aqua, non quomodolibet, sed una refectione ex pane azymo subcineratio, vel cocto in craticula; aut certe farina avenacea incocta, aqua vero lacustri, sed cocta vel saltem calefacta in cacabo, citra salem, aut aliud quodcunque condimentum, atque ista tam cruda et macilenta alimonia, quamvis freudentibus intestinis non nisi semel degustanda erit spatio vigintiquatuor horarum, nisi quod aretes fauces licitum sit refrigerare saepius, quando sitis urgeret»].

In addition to that, before entering the Purgatory the pilgrims' thirst was finally quenched by supplying them with a special sort of water:

«The quality of this water is rather stagnant, and it can be swallowed in any quantity as one wishes, without sensing any heaviness, like if it flew from a metal-rich spring, as if it were a mineral water pouring out from a small spring of sour water».

[In the original Latin text: «Ea vis istius aquae quamvis stagnantis, ut quantumvis ex ea te velis ingurgitare, nullum inde gravamen sentias, perinde ac si ex vena metallica flueret, quod de aqua Spadana ex fonticulo acido emanante perhibent, qui eam epotârunt, absque onere suo vel stomachi gravamine.»].

Fig. 117 - The quality of the water at Station Island, from Thomas Messingham's *Florilegium insulae sanctorum seu Vitae et acta sanctorum Hiberniae* (Paris, 1624), p. 95

We must certainly note that «the streams supplying the lake flow over a wide stretch of bog and moorland. In addition to this, numerous chalybeate springs throughout the lake and around its shores are constantly sending forth streams of reddish liquid, thus tinging the lake with a deeper dye», a reason for the lake's name ('Lough Derg', 'Red Lake' in ancient Irish), as

Daniel O'Connor writes in his *St. Patrick's Purgatory, Lough Derg* (Dublin, 1895).

Thus, just before the passage through the Purgatory's door, the pilgrims were given a tangy, metallic water, possibly the same stagnant waters, rich with gases and minerals, flowing into the lake from the peaty moorland.

Fig. 118 - William of Lisle and the experience of the Purgatory of St. Patrick from Jean Froissart's *Chroniques* (manuscript Français 2646, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folium 196v)

And another astounding clue we can retrieve in a French writer of the Middle Ages, Jean Froissart, who dedicates a few words to St. Patrick's Purgatory in his *Chroniques*, written before the end of the fourteenth century. In Book IV, Chapter CXCVI of his verbose work, Froissart recounts the words that an English gentleman, William of Lisle, had told him about his own visit to the Purgatory. And William's words are of high relevance:

«When I and my companion had crossed the door of the cellar which is called the Purgatory of St. Patrick, and went down three or four steps (because you have to go down as if it were a cellar), a great heat got to our heads, and when we sat on the stony floor, while sitting there, we were overwhelmed by a great longing for sleep, and so we slept all the night through».

[In the original French text: «Quant moy et mon compaignon eusmes passé la porte du cellier, que on appelle le Purgatoire Saint-Patris et nous feusmes descendus trois ou quatre pas (car on y descent ainsi que à un cellier), chalour noust prist ens es testes, et nous asseismes sur les pas qui sont de pierre, et, nous assis, très-grant voulenté nous vint de dormir, et dormismes toute la nuit»].

They slept. And, in their sleep, «they wandered through amazing reveries and astounding dreams, and saw, they reckoned, too many things than they used to dream while sleeping in their beds» («ils entrèrent en ymaginations moult grandes et songes merueilleux, et veoient, ce leur sambloit, en dormant trop plus de choses qu'ils n'eussent fait en leurs chambres sur leurs lits»). So they thought, afterwards, that «it was just visions» («ce soit toute fantosme»).

Fig. 119 - The dreams of William of Lisle within the Purgatory of St. Patrick as reported in Jean Froissart's *Chroniques* (manuscript Français 2646, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folium 196v)

«To sleep - perchance to dream», as Shakespeare's Hamlet would say. And we must remember that Antonio Mannini slept, as well: «As I was praying I fell asleep...» (in the original Italian text: «Così orando m'addormentai...»). And William Staunton writes the following: «And there y abode, and sumwhat slumbered and slepte...».

After their entrance into the Purgatory of St. Patrick, the pilgrims, exhausted by the many days of preparatory penitence, worn-out by the lack of food, frosted by Ireland's cold weather, haunted by the terrorizing anticipations of what awaited them in that hollow, their minds already beholding Hell and its demons, their bellies filled with stagnant, mineral water of a strange quality, when they were finally restricted within the narrow subterranean vault, they were overcome, in the stifling air, by some mephitic vapour, which issued perhaps from the bodies of their companions laying very close, or maybe even pouring in from the strata of decaying peat which enshrouded Lough Derg and its cave.

And they had dreams. Dreams of the afterlife. Dreams of the Otherworld.

Was all that, maybe, the odd condensation of a peculiar nature which marked St. Patrick's Purgatory, at Lough Derg, in Ireland? Were the pilgrims' nighmarish dreams being aroused by mephitic gases and vapours filling the small volume of the subterranean vault? Were such dreams also powered by the stagnant water which filled their stomachs, and by the physical exhaustion being experienced by the Purgatory's visitors following many days of remorseful fast?

We must remember that Lough Derg is located in a territory rich in peatlands and bogs. And peatlands, marshes and bogs generate significant amounts of a very special gas: methane, a colourless and odorless gas which originates from decaying plants in low-oxygen environments.

Methane, as scientists know, though non-toxic, may induce asphyxiation as it reduces oxygen levels in the body and brain. People exposed to methane get initially dizzy and their hearts undergo rapid palpitation, a symptom that can be easily mistaken for a sensation of utter, terrific fear; then they fall asleep, with a significant risk of death ensuing while they are unconscious. As the body is missing oxygen, it tries to retrieve it from the blood, so inducing a dehydration effect (a symptom of which the managers

of St. Patrick's Purgatory seemed to be well aware, for they urged the visitors to drink as much water as they wanted before entering the cave, as reported by Thomas Messingham).

Fig. 120 - A close-up of the entrance to St. Patrick's Purgatory as it appears in the second edition of James Ware's *De Hibernia et antiquitatibus ejus, disquisitiones* (London, 1658, p. 222)

With methane filling the small cave to the ceiling, the brain of the pilgrims began to suffer from lack of oxygen. Contemporary medical studies show that an on-going asphyxiation process interferes with the production of serotonin, a neurotransmitter. And the modification of serotonin levels can induce hallucinations and altered states of consciousness. As a matter of fact, a state of anoxia can be marked by the presence of hallucinatory experiences.

Of course, the author of the present paper is no medical doctor, and certainly it is beyond the scope of the present research to probe further into this tricky though promising topic, which scholars have already analysed with reference to the prophecies rendered by the sibilline oracle at the Temple of Apollo at Delphi, Greece, under the possible influence of mephitic vapors, following the indication provided in the first century by Plutarch, the great Greek writer. And we also saw, in a previous paragraph,

that mephitic vapors filled the hollows in Cumae, which the people reputed as the caves of the Cumaean Sibyl, and we know that many fell dead in them in search of treasures and evanescent dreams.

Nonetheless, it is clear that mythical tales often tread very odd paths, and when they settle down at a specific place, like Lough Derg, that place is not a place whatsoever: it is always a special one.

Fig. 121 - Pilgrims on their way to Station Island in a print from Daniel O'Connor's *St. Patrick's Purgatory, Lough Derg* (Dublin, 1895, p. 208-209)

As we already stated in previous paragraphs, attraction of myths and generation of legends in connection to specific geographical locations is definitely a main issue we are trying to investigate within the framework of the research we are carrying out on the Sibillini Mountain Range and its legendary heritage.

A lake, Lough Derg, and its deadly cave: the specific nature of the place, possibly linked to the local generation of mephitic, hallucination-inducing gases, made up a suitable setting to stage a terrific narrative concerning the

Christian Purgatory and its harrowing punishments. That's why the site of St. Patrick's Purgatory became, like Cumae, another famous, recognised 'hot spot' in Europe providing living men with a further mythical access to the Otherworld.

This is another crack. An additional fissure. A further crevice dug in our usual world, another horrific break pierced in the souls of the frightened mortals.

Again, the landmark, the distinctive emblem, is made up by a lake and a cave.

And we will see that these very same considerations will apply to the Sibillini Mountain Range, too.

4.4 Further mythical affinities: Lough Derg and the Sibillini Mountain Range

In the previous paragraphs, we illustrated the mythical tale of Cumae, featuring a Lake Avernus and a nearby cave which, in classical antiquity, was believed to provide an access to the Otherworld. We also highlighted the narrative connections that linked this Cumaean tale, widely known throughout Europe owing to its presence in Vergil's *Aeneid*, and the legends which inhabited the Sibillini Mountain Range, provided with its own Cave and Lake.

But affinities are not over. We also saw that a northern-European country, Ireland, housed another legendary tale: again, a lake, Lough Dergh, and a cave, which was the entryway to another Otherworld, the Purgatory of St. Patrick. And this tale, as well, was widely known throughout Europe, and also in the Italian peninsula and, specifically, as we will see later in this same article, in central Italy.

A most significant example of the widespread renown of the Purgatory of St. Patrick is provided by the *Legenda Aurea*, the collection of tales about the life and death of more than a hundred fifty saints which was written by

Jacobus de Varagine, a Dominican friar and bishop from the Italian town of Genoa, in the second half of the thirteenth century.

The *Legenda Aurea* was a most successful work, a sort of 'best seller' for many centuries, with thousands of manuscripts still extant. It was considered by preachers as a convenient source of themes and topics, and was read by all sorts of audiences, owing to the fascinating stories it contained about the impressive, moving martyrdoms of holy men and women, and the overall readability of the text, written in a simple, tough fluent, Latin.

And the *Legenda Aurea*, in its Chapter XLIX, which immediately followed the section dedicated to a most venerated saint, Benedict of Norcia, did not overlook the Purgatory of St. Patrick at all:

Fig. 122 - The indication of the chapter dedicated to St. Patrick in the manuscript's summary and the opening of the same chapter from Jacobus de Varagine's *Legenda Aurea* (fourteenth-century manuscript Latin 9730, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folia 1v and 83v)

«The Lord commanded that he [St. Patrick] drew on a certain spot a large circle on the ground with his staff, and immediately the ground within the circle opened up and there appeared a pit of unfathomable depth; and it was

revealed to St. Patrick that there was the entrance to the Purgatory; whoever entered therein he should never suffer other punishments, nor experience the purgatory out of his sins. Many should never return from it, and those who come back should stay in it no more than one single day. And many entered that came not again».

[In the original Latin text: «Jussu igitur domini in quodam loco magnum circulum cum baculo designavit et ecce terra inter circulum se aperuit et puteus maximus et profundissimus ibi apparuit revelatumque est beato Patricio, quod ibi purgatorii locus esset, in quem quisquis vellet descendere, alia sibi poenitentia non restaret nec aliud pro peccatis sentiret purgatorium, plerique autem indem non redirent et qui redirent eos a mane usque in sequens mane ibidem moram facere oporteret. Multi igitur ingrediebantur, qui de caetero non revertebantur»].

Fig. 123 - St. Patrick is shown the entrance to the Purgatory from Jacobus de Varagine's *Legenda Aurea* (fourteenth-century manuscript Latin 9730, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folium 84r)

This is the description of the legend of St. Patrick's Purgatory as contained in the chapter dedicated to the Irish saint in the *Legenda Aurea*, a passage

which is patently drawn from Henry of Saltrey's *Tractatus de Purgatorio Sancti Patricii*.

Jacobus de Varagine did not miss the chance to include in his own work the full story of the thrilling descent of Owein into the Purgatory of St. Patrick, so his account proceeds further, with a change in the name of the main character:

«A certain nobleman whose name was Nicholaus, who had committed many sins [...] decided to enter the Purgatory of St. Patrick. So he first exhausted himself by abstaining from food for fifteen days, as everybody used to do; then, the door was unlocked with the key that was preserved at the Abbey, and into the hollow he went...»

[In the original Latin text: «Quidam vir nobilis nomine Nicholaus, qui peccata multa commiserat [...] purgatorium sancti Patricii sustinere vellet, cum antea quindecim diebus, ut omnes faciebant, se ieiuniis macerasset, aperto ostio cum clavi, quae in quadam abbatia servabatur, in praedictum puteum descendit...»].

Fig. 124 - Nicholas and his entrance into the Purgatory from Jacobus de Varagine's *Legenda Aurea* (fourteenth-century manuscript Latin 9730, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folium 84r)

Then a long account of Nicholas' travel into the Purgatory follows, similarly drawn from the work written by Henry of Saltrey. He meets the same men dressed in white, who advise him to invoke the name of Jesus when undergoing the Purgatory's excruciating tortures («cum te poenis affligi senseris, protinus clama et dic: 'Jesu Christe fili Dei vivi miserere mihi peccatori»), an appeal to which Guerrino the Wretch will often resort as well in the romance written by Andrea da Barberino.

Fig. 125 - The salvific invocation of the name of Jesus Christ as it appears in Jacobus de Varagine's *Legenda Aurea* (thirteenth-century manuscript NAL 1747, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folium 85r)

Then terrible purgatorial punishments begin to be presented to him by the demons. The usual visions of fire and hooks and fiendish whips which we already know from Henry of Saltrey, including the most famous wheel of fire («rota maxima erat uncinis ferreis ignitis plena...») are also described by Jacobus. And the *Legenda Aurea* does not forget to report about the well-known otherworldly 'test bridge' device, which, as we already know, we will also find in the Sibyl's Cave:

«He was led to a place in which a bridge stood [...] that was utterly narrow and polished and slippery as ice; under the bridge a river of sulphureous fire was flowing, so that it seemed impossible to cross it [...] He confidently entered the bridge and put a foot on it, as he began to utter the words 'Jesus Christ etc.' [...] At each step he treaded, he pronounced these words and crossed safely».

[In the original Latin text: «Ductus igitur ad alium locum vidit quendam pontem [...] qui quidem erat strictissimus et instar glaciei politus et lubricus, sub quo fluvius ingens sulphureus et igneus fluebat, super quem dum se posse transire omnino desperaret [...] confidenter accessit et unum pedem super pontem ponens, Jesu Christe etc. dicere coepit [...] ad quemlibet passum eadem verba protulit et sic securus transivit»].

Fig. 126 - The 'test bridge' as described in Jacobus de Varagine's *Legenda Aurea* (fourteenth-century manuscript Latin 9730, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folium 84v)

The amazing legend of the Purgatory of St. Patrick was fully known in Italy, with its cave described by Henry of Saltrey and its lake, mentioned by Gerald of Wales, and a thorough illustration elaborated by Jacobus de Varagine. And we can easily show that, in the fourteenth century, the legend was perfectly known in central Italy as well, in a place that was only 45 miles away from the Sibillini Mountain Range. In 1346, Jacopo di Mino del Pellicciaio, an artist from Siena, painted an astounding fresco on a wall of the refectory of the convent of San Francesco al Borgo Nuovo at Todi, Umbria. The fresco portrays exactly *The Purgatory of St. Patrick*: a remarkable witness to the success of the Irish legendary tale in a central-Italian cultural environment.

Fig. 127 - *The Purgatory of St. Patrick*, a fourteenth-century fresco painted by Jacopo di Mino del Pellicciaio (Convent of San Francesco al Borgo Nuovo, Todi, Umbria, Italy)

A lake and a cave in Ireland, which provided a legendary entryway to an Otherworld. Another Lake and another Cave in central Italy, for which tales were told about necromancy and demons.

In a previous paragraph, we already noted that, in the Middle Ages, whoever had any memory of classical antiquity he would associate the site set amid the Apennines with Cumae, its lake and cave, and an ancient Sibyl.

But another narrative association was also possible.

Everybody knew of the medieval legend of the Purgatory of St. Patrick, too, with its lake and terrific cave. A legendary tale that was fully reported in the most-renowned and widely-read *Legenda Aurea*. So, any eerie tale concerning a further Lake and Cave in the Apennines, marked by some magical or otherworldly characters, would immediately bring to the listener's mind that sinister, far-away Purgatory.

Oral storytellers and, later in time, men of letters could not keep away from incurring some sort of combination of the two mutually extraneous narratives: a lake and cave set in northern Ireland, and the Lake and Cave lying in a massif which is part of the Apennine mountainous chain. Precisely the same contamination process, wholly natural as a tale spreads amid audiences across the centuries, which led to a combination of the sibilline tale in the Apennines and the legend established in Cumae since classical antiquity.

So, once more, we find that the geographical landmarks set amid the Apennines generated an attractive pull for a different legendary tale, which in this case came from Ireland: and the result is the incorporation of themes and suggestions linked to the Purgatory of St. Patrick into the Sibillini Mountain Range's legendary tradition, despite its being set in a different territory altogether.

Again, the mythical tale of an otherworldly entryway accessible by men in Ireland experienced a partial migration to the area of the Sibillini Mountain Range, as oral storytellers added details and spice to their accounts concerning an icy Lake and a Cave set on a cliff, both lost in a secluded region of the Italian Apennines. Again. If a passageway to the afterlife existed in Ireland, this was to be considered as an occurrence, mythical as it was, which provided further strength to the Italian tale, out of an easily-noticeable similarity between the two locations, both marked by the presence of a lake and a cave.

Of course, the Purgatory of St. Patrick has nothing to do with the Apennines; nonetheless, their respective legendary narratives underwent some degree of combination, as already illustrated in our previous articles *St. Patrick's Purgatory, a source for Guerrino and Antoine de La Sale*, *Antoine de La Sale and the magical bridge concealed beneath Mount Sibyl* and *Birth of a Sibyl: the medieval connection*.

This process can be detected in both literary works which, in the fifteenth century, marked the starting point of the European-wide success of the legend of an Apennine Sibyl: Andrea da Barberino's romance "Guerrino the Wretch" and Antoine de la Sale's account *Paradise of Queen Sibyl*.

Needless to say, both authors had full acquaintance with the myth of Lough Derg and its Purgatory.

Antoine de la Sale clearly signals the above fact when, in his work *La Salade*, he includes a direct reference to the Irish legend of St. Patrick:

«The isle of Ireland, very close to England, is wide and primitive, and the local people too. A church dedicated to St. Patrick is found there and there is also the cave in which people say that the punishments of Purgatory and the torments of Hell can be seen».

[In the original French text: «L'ysle de yrlande ioinct assez pres dangleterre est elle moult grande et sausvaige et les gens aussi leglise saint Patrisse y est et la est la caue ou se dit que on va veoir les peines de purgatoire et les tourmens denfer»].

Fig. 128 - Ireland and the Purgatory of St. Patrick as mentioned in Antoine de la Sale's *La Salade* (Paris, 1527)

When Antoine de la Sale writes his account of his own visit to a Lake and a Cave in central Apennines, he introduces in his narration a few details which appear to be drawn from extraneous material concerning journeys to the Otherworld, with a specific reference to the legend he thoroughly knew, the Purgatory of St. Patrick, featuring its own lake and cave. And the first

detail, as we already indicated at the beginning of the present research article, is the 'test bridge':

«Then you find a bridge, made of some unknown material, but it is said to be less than a single foot wide and it seems to be extending far ahead. Below the bridge, a ghastly, precipitating abyss [...] Yet as soon as you put both feet on the bridge, it becomes large enough; and the more you step ahead, the more it widens and the abyss becomes shallower».

[In the original French text: «Lors trouve-l'on un pont, que l'on ne scet de quoy il est, mais est advis qu'il n'ait mie un pied de large et semble estre moult long. Dessoubz ce pont, a très grant et hydeux abisme de parfondeur [...] Mais aussitost que on a les deux pieds sur ce pont, il est assez large; et tant vait on plus avant tant est plus large et moins creux»].

Fig. 129 - The 'test bridge' included by Antoine de la Sale in his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folia 11v and 12r)

We know that the magically narrow bridge is present in many other otherworldly accounts, including St. Gregory the Great's *Dialogues*, the *Vision of St. Adamnán* and the *Vision of Tnugdalus*; nonetheless, in the

fifteenth century whoever read the words written by Antoine de la Sale would jump back, in his own mind, to the most famous and most impressive 'test bridge' of all its kindred, i.e. the one portrayed in Henry of Saltrey's *Tractatus de Purgatorio Sancti Patricii* and its subsequent description as reported by Jacobus de Varagine in his widely-known *Legenda Aurea*.

In addition to that, we also stumble upon an amazing pictorial contamination between the legend of St. Patrick's Purgatory and the description of the Sibyl's Cave as provided by Antoine de la Sale in his gorgeous illuminated account *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*, which we find in manuscript no. 0653 (0924) preserved at the Bibliothèque du Château - Musée Condé in Chantilly, France.

At folium 9v, the French gentleman provides a portrait of himself on the top of Mount Sibyl as he enters the narrow passageway to the Cave.

Fig. 130 - Antoine de la Sale enters into the Sibyl's Cave, from *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 9v)

But a strikingly similar miniature is preserved in manuscript Français 1544, preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France and dating to at least fifty years earlier. At folium 105r, we find a pilgrim daringly entering the cave which leads into St. Patrick's Purgatory, at Lough Derg.

Fig. 131 - Entrance to the Purgatory of St. Patrick from *La tres noble et tres merveilleuse Histoire du purgatoire saint Patrice* (manuscript Français 1544, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folium 105r)

Fig. 132 - A penitent knight enters the Purgatory of St. Patrick, from a French version of the *Legenda Aurea* (manuscript Additional 17275, British Library, London, folia 191v and 192v)

And other comparable images are found in manuscript Additional 17275 preserved at the British Library in London: two miniatures associated to a French version of the *Legenda Aurea* and its description of St. Patrick's Purgatory, dating to the mid of the fourteenth century, a clear sign that the pictorial representations of the mythical Irish purgatorial access were markedly similar to the idea of an entryway to a magical or otherworldly realm set amid the Italian Apennines.

A sort of representation we also find in later centuries, again in connection with St. Patrick's Purgatory and the *Legenda Aurea*, like the one we retrieve in manuscript no. 672-5 II preserved at the Morgan Library in New York (folium 178v), dating to the second half of the fifteenth century.

Fig. 133 - A pilgrim enters the Purgatory of St. Patrick (manuscript no. 672-5 II, Morgan Library, New York, folium 178v)

We cannot tell whether Antoine de la Sale ever saw the versions in French of the legend of the Purgatory of St. Patrick contained in the two earlier manuscripts, the Français 1544 and the Additional 17275; however, it seems apparent that similarities between the Purgatory in Ireland and the Sibyl's Cave in Italy do exist in terms of narrative choices that Antoine de

la Sale made when editing his account concerning a visit to an entryway to a fiendish realm hidden amid the Italian Apennines. For we must be aware, as we already pointed out in our previous article *Sibillini Mountain Range: the legend before the legends*, that Antoine de la Sale considered the Italian Cave as an evil place inhabited by a «fake Sibyl» («faulse Sibille») of demonic origin, in which men confronted with «all wraiths and Devil's contrivances [...] through which the demons used to deceive people» («toutes fantosmes et toutes deableries [...] de quoy les deables decevoient le gens»). A demonic place which housed wicked demons, not unlike the Irish Purgatory.

If we now come to Andrea da Barberino, we stumble upon further connections and similarities. The Italian writer proves to be far more straight than Antoine de la Sale was. His reference to the Purgatory of St. Patrick is so patent and extended that we cannot fail to miss it when we read his romance *Guerrino the Wretch*.

At the very end of the section dedicated to the Sibyl, Andrea da Barberino sends his knight hero, Guerrino, right into the Purgatory of St. Patrick, in Ireland, as a penitence imparted to him by the Pope for having been at the forbidden court of the Apennine Sibyl:

«The Holy Father spoke to him: 'You are blessed' [...] and, as a penitence, he commanded to him, the way he had dared violate God's edict not to enter the abode of the Sibyl and visit illusory idols, to go to the Purgatory of St. Patrick, which is under the rule of the Archbishop of Hibernia in the island called Ireland».

[In the original Italian text: «El santo padre li disse: 'tu sei benedetto" [...] e per penitenzia impose como lui havea havuto ardire contra el comandamento de la leze de dio de intrare dove stava la Sibilla et de andare a visitare li idoli [...] chusì volea che per comandamento lui andasse a lo purgatorio de santo Patritio el quale è sotto l'arcivescovo de Ibernia in l'ixola dita Irlanda»].

The journey of Guerrino into the Irish Purgatory immediately follows his stay at the Sibyl's subterranean realm, the former being a penance imparted to the knight for having visited the latter: a sign that a narrative connection exists in Andrea da Barberino's mind, with the demonic presence at the

Sibyl's Cave linked with the demons which inhabit the purgatorial cavern, out of a common otherworldly character. We will also see that the very same uttering of the name of Jesus Christ will dispel the demonic powers present at both caves, another token of the common narrative traits that link the two episodes.

Fig. 134 - Guerrino is sent to the Purgatory of St. Patrick in Ireland, from Andrea da Barberino's *Guerrino the Wretch* (Chapter CLVII of the edition printed in Venice in 1480)

The author of *Guerrino the Wretch* proves to be well acquainted with the Irish legend, as his knight hero undergoes the same introductory procedure to the Purgatory as we already know from the writings of Henry of Saltrey. On his arrival in Ireland, he asks for the special permission to be issued by the local bishop. The bishop makes his usual attempts at changing the pilgrim's mind by addressing him with the customary warnings:

«You are about to expose yourself to serious danger, for many who went in never came back».

[In the original Italian text: «Tu te meti a tanto pericolo, ipero che molti vi sono andati che non sono tornati»].

de' santo Patritio: doue purgeria tuti li soi peccati . Disse lo arcivescouo
io non uoio che tu te meti a tanto periculo: ipero che molti ui sono anda
ti che non sono tornati. ma tu porai fare una fanta uita: e stare in questo

Fig. 135 - The bishop's warning to Guerrino on the dangers awaiting him in the Purgatory of St. Patrick, from Andrea da Barberino's *Guerrino the Wretch* (Chapter CLXII of the edition printed in Venice in 1480)

Then the bishop sends him to the island where the Purgatory lies, with a presentation letter to be delivered to the prior of the adjacent church. Guerrino goes through the usual nine days of fast, prayer and penitence. Before the entrance to the Purgatory, a huge cavern which proceeded under the ground, («una grandissima caverna che andava sotto terra»), he is given by the prior the same advice as he was told by the hermits before entering the Sibyl's Cave, with the recommendation to utter the same invocation as pronounced by Henry of Saltrey's knight, Owein, in his *Tractatus de Purgatorio Sancti Patricii*:

ternante che ne fecerle bene
apoueri p lo amore de dio e
pregolo che prestile spio p
lui. Labate li feete date uno
picolo pane diuenoli qste
e dilpane di Santo patritio
porale in seruo / elete uenisse
fame / et ne manzia uno pecho
etecelo comonichate. Sueri
no li adimando di portate sic
cho laspada / elgi bene Raye
drite / ho chautate in questo
luoco / no gli bixegna a me
di fero. Ma te bixogna esse
amato di amore et de feda
di chaito et di speranza / nel
nome de xpo xpo et alme a
me Se tu ne auenti quant
ne sono Sepa latera / no ti
uarebano mente. a) a tien
amente quello te dico / aze
tu no peccata p ignozan
tia / quando tu entezai nela
chaucerna / et tu segna / et
intato / nela chaucerna alee
rai la mano acielo / ed i xhu
nazareno xpo nel tuo nome
saluz me fact / et abia semp
quelle parole amente / et p
che tu dia hominatate / ho
teptate da demoni / no me
nate anima chonli che vol
giano date / ma de tuto quello
te adimandezano fa el gnatio
et no li obedire / odandate / adi
tornate / ne p promesse ne p
uerana chonli / e questo fiolo
mie abia amere / e sepa tuto
no rimmentate. xhu
no xpo / nel tuo nome
me fact / e quando de
ti farano al chuna / no
no ti turbate / no ti /
teina a quello parole
tuti filquelo chome
diete Sarai libero de
molesta / p quella lo
chum farai bogni /
stazano in xhu /
potti patire / ma quan
toz pena te darano
Selezai patiente p
de dio tanto piu me
figuete / ni tonerai /
ndere / in xhu alo /
purgatorio / bna /
picta / la quale e imga bene
veno migro / et he molto ho
bistura / et enebro / et del
monta che tu arai / la chala
tonerai / bna / nona / plaquale
andrai / gram pezo / poi
tonerai / la luce / eguante
rai in dno posto / enel me
gite / tonerai / bna /
nela quale tu entezai / di

Fig. 136 - Guerrino's invocation in the Purgatory of St. Patrick, an utterance already raised by another knight, Owein, in the same predicament, from Andrea da Barberino's *Guerrino the Wretch* (manuscript no. MA297, Biblioteca Civica *Angelo Mai*, Bergamo, folium 157r)

«When you will enter the cave, cross yourself, and after your entrance raise your hand to the heaven while saying 'Jesus Christ of Nazareth, in your name make me safe'».

[In the original Italian text: «Quando tu entrerai nela chaverna, e tu ti segna, et intrato nela chaverna alzerai la mano a cielo e di' Iesu Nazareno Christo nel tuo nome salvum me fach'»].

And Guerrino the Wretch is locked into St. Patrick's Purgatory. The same way as knight Owein was.

In the Purgatory, Guerrino undergoes the same demonic trials as described by Henry of Saltrey, with a concurrent, patent effort to revisit narrative schemes contained in Dante Alighieri's *Divine Comedy*. After the encounter with the usual men dressed in white robes, Guerrino is seized by the demons and brought to the punishments we already know, including the well-known, huge wheel provided with pointed hooks («grandissima rota con denti de ferro aguzi»).

As we already noticed in our previous article *Antoine de La Sale and the magical bridge concealed beneath Mount Sibyl*, Guerrino also meets the well-known 'test bridge', which - it is to be reminded - Antoine de la Sale liked to place in the Sibyl's Cave:

«... and immediately he was standing on a bridge that crossed the marsh from one side to the other over a large river. And it seemed to him that the bridge was so narrow that nobody could have put one foot ahead of the other. He turned to get back but he could not see the bridge beneath his own eyes. And he saw countless jaws of big snakes and dragons, and it was as if they were waiting for him to fall down. Guerrino had never been so scared as in this predicament. And all the way along the bridge he feared he would fall. And actually he was about to fall: but he called on the Holy Name, and by His mercy the bridge swell to a huge width. And he could go through this perilous passage».

[In the original Italian text: «... e subito fu drito sopra uno ponte che trapassava questo lagune da uno lato al altro sopra uno grande fiume. E parevali questo ponte tanto sottile, che uno piede avanti l'altro non li poteva stare. Lui se volse per tornare e non vide el ponte abasso gli ochi. E vide

infinite bocche de grandi serpenti, e dragoni, e pareua che aspetassero che lui cadesse. Anchora non havea avuto Guerino magior paura che questa. E tutta via li pareua de cadere. E pure saria caduto: ma chiamò el santo nome, e per la soa misericordia el ponte se li fece larghissimo. E passò de là da questo fortunoso passo»].

Fig. 137 - The two different excerpts in which Guerrino encounters the same magical bridge, from Andrea da Barberino's *Guerrino the Wretch* (Chapters CLXX and CLXXXII of the edition printed in Venice in 1480)

The whole narrative is so expanded and redundant that Guerrino even stumbles upon a second 'test bridge':

«And he saw a river that was crossed by so thin and narrow a bridge that there was no small animal that would pass through it, because of his tiny width. He crossed himself and entrusted himself to God. He was taken [by the demons] and placed onto the middle of the bridge, where they left him, then they began to scream at him, and flung stones and shafts at him so that he was about to fall. And he turned to go back, and could see no bridge. So he looked at the bottom where the water was, and saw that it was full of hideous worms and snakes. The bridge was so thin that it was not possible to put one foot ahead of the other. He began to call the name of Jesus Christ from Nazareth, and the bridge started to get larger. As he spoke these words thrice, he began to sing 'Domine ne in furore tuo arguas me', and the bridge became even larger, and he was through».

[In the original Italian text: «e vide uno fiume cui atraverso li era uno ponte tanto sutile e stretto che lo non è si piccolo animale che havesse potuto passare, tanto era stretto. Lui se fece el segno de la santa croce e recomandose a dio. Fu preso [dai demoni] e posto suxo el mezo del ponte et ivi lo lassorono, e poi cominciarono a cridare et a zitarli pietre e pali per modo che el meschino fu per cadere. E lui se volse indietro per tornare indietro, e non vide ponte. Alhora pose mente nel fundo de laqua, e lo vide pieno de vermini bruti e serpenti. El ponte era si stretto che uno pié inanti l'altro non li cadeva. Lui cominciò a chiamare iesu christo nazareno, e lo ponte si cominciò a largare. E dite queste parole tre volte, cominciò a cantare 'Domine ne in furore tuo arguas me', et el ponte se largava, e lui passò»].

Following this verbose description of purgatorial punishments, Guerrino attains the Paradise and is finally brought back by angels to the initial chamber of the Purgatory. The door is unlocked and the prior celebrates his safe return to the world of the living, the way is described in Henry of Saltrey *Tractatus de Purgatorio Sancti Patricii*.

Before crossing the door, Guerrino asks the accompanying angels his fateful question about his own lineage, still unknown to him. And he gets the answer he has been earnestly looking for throughout the entire romance:

fezmi di dio so vi priego che bui
me insignati che mio padre in
po che p' s'afani etatiche nō mi
sono aricordato di dimandare

queli fezmi de dio li disse nō
ti sgomentare che tu sei di schia
ta Reale et in nitalia simoue

Fig. 138 - The kingly lineage of Guerrino is revealed to him at the end of his visit into St. Patrick's Purgatory, from Andrea da Barberino's *Guerrino the Wretch* (manuscript no. MA297, Biblioteca Civica Angelo Mai, Bergamo, folia 174v and 175r)

«I beseech you, that you tell me who my father is [...] You are of kingly descent»

[In the original Italian text: «Io vi priego che vui me insignati chie mio padre [...] Tu sei di schiata Reale»].

Thus, in Andrea da Barberino's romance, Guerrino the Wretch travels into a subterranean Otherworld of demons and purgatorial punishments, as a sequel to a previous journey made into another subterranean realm, that of the Sibyl, similarly inhabited by demonic presences. And the narrative connection between the two episodes is confirmed by the fact that here, at St. Patrick's Purgatory, Guerrino is finally given the answer that was repeatedly denied to him in the preceding otherworldly travel, when the Sibyl had refused to unveil his lineage to him:

«O much wise Sibyl I beseech you by your power, that you consent to tell me who my ancestry was, and who my father and mother were [...] From me you won't get any other information apart from what you know already».

Fig. 139 - The Apennine Sibyl rejects all attempts effected by Guerrino to have his own lineage revealed, from Andrea da Barberino's *Guerrino the Wretch* (pages 137v and 138r of the edition printed in Padua in 1473)

[In the original Italian text: «O sapientissima Sibilla io te prego per la tua virtu chel te sia de piazere de dirme chui sono li mei antichi et cui e el mio padre e la mia madre [...] Da mi non saperesti nessuna cossa piui inanzi de quello che tu sa»].

The Sibillini Mountain Range and its legends. The mythical tale of St. Patrick's Purgatory. Both feature a lake and a cave. Both are inhabited by demons and marked by otherworldly characters. It is not a surprise that we find a transfer of narrative topics and situations from the illustrious and widely-known Irish tale, to an Italian tale with some narrative traits in common, despite the total independence of the two legendary settings.

There is no direct connection between the two legends. However, a contamination of narrative themes was certainly fostered by the mutual similarities which plainly marked the two sites: two lakes, two eerie caverns, both providing an access to an Otherworld, a purgatorial afterlife in Ireland and a subterranean, demonic realm in the Italian Apennines. A contamination that travelled across the centuries of the Middle Ages, through an invisible streams of oral tales and storytelling, which finally materialised within the fifteenth-century works written by Antoine de la Sale and Andrea da Barberino.

And another significant common trait exists.

To highlight it, we must go back to the ghastly words written by Gerald of Wales (Giraldus Cambrensis) in his *Topographia Hibernica*, dating to the year 1188.

In describing the Purgatory of St. Patrick, Gerald writes the following sentence:

«There is a lake in Ulster containing an island divided into two parts. [...] The other part, being covered with rugged crags, is reported to be the resort of devils only, and to be almost always the theatre on which crowds of evil spirits who visibly perform their rites [...] This part of the island contains nine pits, and should anyone perchance venture to spend the night in one of them [...], he is immediately seized by the malignant spirits, who so severely torture him during the whole night, inflicting on him such unutterable sufferings by fire and water, and other torments of various

kinds, that when morning comes scarcely any spark of life is found left in his wretched body».

[In the original Latin text: «Est lacus in partibus Ultoniae continens insulam bipartitam. [...] Pars altera, hispida nimis et horribilis, solis daemoniis dicitur assignata; quae et visibilibus cacodaemonum turbis et pompis fere semper manet exposita [...] Pars ista novem in se foveas habet. In quarum aliqua si quis forte pernoctare praesumpserit, [...] a malignis spiritibus statim arripitur, et nocte tota tam gravibus poenis cruciatur, tot tantisque et tam ineffabilis ignis et aquae variique generis tormentis incessanter affligitur, ut mane facto vix vel minimae spiritus superstitis reliquiae misero in corpore reperiantur»].

Fig. 140 - Left: the demonic island of St. Patrick's Purgatory as it appears in Gerald of Wales' Topographia Hibernica (manuscript no. Ff.1.27, Cambridge University Library, folium 294); Right: the demonic Lake of Norcia as it appears in Petrus Berchorius' Reductorium Morale (manuscript Latin 16786, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folium 301v)

But the above words strongly bring to our mind another Lake, and the description provided of it by Petrus Berchorius in the fourteenth century:

«Amid the peaks which raise near that town [Norcia] there is a lake, which from antique times is sacred to demons and conspicuously inhabited by them [...] each year that town sends a single man, a living man, beyond the

walls that encircle the lake, as an offering to the demons, who immediately and in full view tear apart and slaughter that man».

[In the original Latin text: «Inter montes isti civitati proximos esse lacum ab antiquis daemonibus consecratum et ab ipsis sensibiliter inhabitatum [...] quia civitas illa omni anno unum hominem vivum pro tributo infra ambitum murorum iuxta lacum ad daemones mittunt, qui statim visibiliter illum hominem lacerant et consumunt»].

An Irish lake with its pits, Lough Derg, and an Italian Lake seem to share a same terrific character: both are inhabited by a same sort of demons; they are visibly and manifestly inhabited by them; people who cross their boundaries are immediately seized; their bodies are tortured and slaughtered.

It is clear that a narrative contamination has been taking place amid the two mutually distant lakes.

And we believe that the keyword to the legendary tale of the Sibillini Mountain Range is, again, Otherworld. An Otherworld that was believed could be accessed by men through a Cave and a Lake. In full analogy with the passageways that were reputed to exist at St. Patrick's Purgatory, Ireland, and Cumae, Italy.

The three tales were very similar. And, in a legendary framework, the Sibillini Mountain Range was fully fit to house a third, fateful, appalling entrance to the Otherworld.

5. Beyond the legendary layers, a chthonian passageway in the central Apennines

At the end of our thrilling journey into the otherwordly character of the legends of the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate, in the Italian Sibillini Mountain Range, let's summarise our extraordinary findings and far-reaching, daring assumptions about a legendary otherwordly passageway which might have been possibly situated, by an antique tradition that has

left some faint traces in the known literature, among the peaks of the central Apennines.

For centuries, amid the cliffs and ravines of the Sibillini Mountain Range, in central Italy, two renowned legends have been telling their tales to the hearts of men coming from all over Europe: the Sibyl's Cave, placed on a crowned mountaintop; and, only a few miles away, the Lake of Pilate, encircled by daunting, precipitous walls of sheer rock. An unchaste Sibyl was believed to dwell in the Cave under the mount, in a subterranean realm full of handsome damsels of a demonic nature. A Roman prefect, that same officer who sent Jesus Christ to the Cross, was reputed to have been cast into the Lake's icy waters, his body as cursed as a part of the Devil's body. Two fifteenth-century authors, Andrea da Barberino and Antoine de la Sale, wrote literary works about the two legends. And the fame of the two sites ran across the nations for hundreds of years.

Fig. 141 - Mount Sibyl, Sibillini Mountain Range, Italy

However, something seems not to add up.

As we already discussed in many previously-published research papers, there is something wrong with all the commonly-accepted legendary framework: a Sibyl, possibly the Cumaean; Pontius Pilate and his tragic doom; centuries and centuries of visits to the two remote, impracticable sites.

A detailed study of the two legendary narratives clearly shows that the Apennine Sibyl is not a classical oracle, but a descendant of Morgan le Fay and her necromantic companion Sebile, two characters which belong to the Matter of Britain and the Arthurian cycle, staged in a number of chivalric romances and poems written centuries earlier in a northern-European setting. A further analysis of the early-Christian and medieval tale concerning Pontius Pilate shows that his many legendary resting places, located in different areas across Europe, have nothing to do with the Italian Apennines.

Fig. 142 - Lakes of Pilate, Sibillini Mountain Range, Italy

So, in our view and as a result of the investigations we have already released, we can confidently assume that no Sibyl has ever lived amid the peaks of the Sibillini Mountain Range. And no Pontius Pilate has ever been cast into any lake in central Italy. The two narratives do not belong to this portion of the land of Italy. The two famous legends are not original. They both settled here coming from distant territories.

But why did they come and settle right here?

If we remove the two literary layers, which are to be considered as additional legendary overlays, and we start to look attentively into the underlying characters of the legends which mark the two sites, the Cave and the Lake in the Sibillini Mountain Range, we run into a number of common features: necromancy was performed at either sites; legendary demons were believed to dwell in both; tempests and devastations were aroused by necromancers when carrying out their rituals.

Something was already there. Something that had nothing to do with Sibyls and antique Roman prefects. Something that seems to preexist the two additional, extraneous legendary layers.

We believe that the correct path we need to tread if we want to unveil the true core of the legends of the Sibillini Mountain Range leads to a specific, and somewhat unexpected, keyword: Otherworld.

Otherworld: a most ancient dream that men have been dreaming since the earliest antiquity when confronting with life and death, mortality and the divine, and, after the rise of the Christian era, the ultimate truths of salvation and punishment.

At a closer scrutiny, thoroughly performed within the present research paper, the legendary tales of the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate appear to be marked by a number of otherworldly narrative elements. In the account written by Antoine de la Sale, a test bridge of supernatural narrowness crosses a frightful abyss, but it gets wider as you tread on it, a typical contrivance dating back to Pope Gregory the Great's *Dialogues* and then present in a number of medieval visionary writings. Metal doors are also present, magically slamming day and night with a ceaseless crushing motion, a sort of device which is found in earlier chivalric works and is

connected to otherworldly descriptions contained in the *Aeneid* and in the Greek myth of the Symplegades. Crystal rooms await the visitors, the clear sign of an afterlife setting. And the Lake is openly indicated as an entrance to Hell in an excerpt drawn from Petrus Berchorius, written in the fourteenth century. The Lake itself is called 'Lake Avernus' in a manuscripted diagram dating to the sixteenth century, thus marking a remarkable narrative correspondance with the famous, classical entryway to the House of Hades set in Cumae.

An entryway to the Otherworld: since time immemorial this has been an impious craving housed in the soul of men. A dream, a desire for a vision of the afterlife, a longing for prohibited communications with the dead, a quest for obtaining forbidden wishes. And the search for an ultimate truth.

In the present paper, we have explored the many literary instances, part of a well-established Western tradition, which narrate the legendary tales of passageways into the Otherworld, in the form of a 'nekyia', the summoning of the shadows of the dead at the entrance of the gloomy realm, or as a 'katabasis', a journey which brings a mortal man through that passageway and into a land of dread. Such are the ghastly journeys performed by visionary heros in the otherworldly literature of the Western culture. In classical antiquity, Ulysses and his visit to Hades, then Aeneas and his journey into the Avernus, with the Cumaean Sibyl as a guide. And subsequently, the visions of early Christianity: St. Paul and his visionary dreams of Hell, Pope St. Gregory I the Great with his soldier, the first in a series of knights travelling to the Otherworld. And, then again, Ireland, with its medieval descriptions of appalling journeys into the excruciating torments and punishments inflicted to the sinners: the *Vision of St. Adamnán*, the *Vision of Tnugdalus*, and the *Purgatory of St. Patrick*.

But only two are the journeys that are utterly special, the travels into the Otherworld par excellence: these are travels that are performed not in a mere vision, but in actual reality. With a man's physical body.

In the Western literary tradition, two are the most renowned places on Earth where to initiate such a horrifying travel. Two 'hot spots'. Two crevices pierced in the continuity of our ordinary world. Two fissures, dreadfully opened to legendary physical visions of a subterranean, chthonian Hell.

The first is at Cumae, by the Lake Avernus, in southern Italy. And the second is at the Purgatory of St. Patrick, Lough Derg, Co. Donegal, in northern Ireland.

At those two sites, living men could be so fool as to make an attempt at crossing the gates which must never be crossed. Two passageways to the Otherworld. Two entryways to an afterlife inhabited by legendary demonic powers.

The two traditional entrances were widely known throughout the Middle Ages and across the entire Europe. They had been the subjects of many literary works, from the *Aeneid* to the *Tractatus de Purgatorio Sancti Patricii* and the *Legenda Aurea*. People engaged themselves in difficult journeys as far as the two listed locations with the aim to see, and cross, the contact points between two worlds, which are normally separated: the world of the living, and the realm of the dead.

By an odd chance, not due to any specific, traceable reason, both sites were indicated by the same pair of landmarks: a lake and a cave for both, two landforms which fully identified the two sites on the surface of Earth, and were known as such.

Why Cumae and Lough Derg? Why did passageways to the Otherworld happen to settle exactly in those two locations? Caves were in the volcanic soil of Cumae, that were filled to the vaulted ceilings with mephitic gases, which induced dreams, and sometimes a horrible death. A cave was also to be found at Lough Derg: on entering, sleep overwhelmed the already exhausted pilgrims, who then dreamt and had nightmares, possibly out of the lack of breathable air, and, maybe, owing to the presence of poisonous gases arising from the marshy ground.

Lake Avernus and its cave at Cumae. Lough Derg and its cave in Ireland. But a third set of landmarks, similarly made up by a Lake and a Cave, was also present in central Italy.

It was the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate in the Sibillini Mountain Range. Set only a few miles away from each other.

The same geographical configuration, as at Cumae and Lough Derg. A demonic presence registered and necromantic rituals being performed at this third Italian site, too. Otherworldly traits, which marked the two landforms amid the Apennines as well.

And we may also try to assume, in centuries which precede the fifteenth, when narratives were only oral and photographic imaging was still centuries ahead, that the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate were essentially close enough to be considered as a single legendary system, without the differentiation of which we still find a trace today in their two distinct names, Sibyl's and Pilate's. It is Antoine de la Sale himself who seems to point to this research direction, when he says the following words at the very opening of his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*:

Fig. 143 - The opening of Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 2v)

«And first I will tell you of the mountain of the lake of Queen Sibyl, which some name the mountain of the lake of Pilate [...] part of the Duchy of Spoletium and in the territory of the town of Norcia»

[In the original French text: «Et premierement, diray du mont du lac de la royne sibille, que aucuns appellent le mont du lac de Pillate [...] parties de la duchié d'Espolit et ou terrouer de la cite de Norse»].

Because the Lake was not a Pilate's Lake, but a Lake of the Sibyl, or a Lake of Norcia, as also reported by Petrus Berchorius in his fourteenth-century

Reductorium Morale. The Lake and Cave in the Sibillini Mountain Range are not distinct, they are part of a same legendary tale.

So we have a lake and a cave in Cumae, a lake and a cave in Ireland, and a further Lake and Cave in the territory of Norcia, amid the Sibillini Mountain Range: each pair of geographical landmarks being a part of a same local legendary framework.

Fig. 144 - Mount Vettore with its glacial cirque in which the Lakes of Pilate are nested, as seen from the slopes of Mount Sibyl

The many similarities which are manifestly found among the three sites, all including a lake and a cave and a local otherwordly tradition, fostered many narrative contaminations, mainly from the two most famous ones to the less known Apennine site. Across many centuries, local residents, wayfarers, oral storytellers and men of letters spread the word about this amazing Lake and Cave concealed amid the ridges of the central Apennines, in Italy, by adding to their wondrous accounts a number of

narrative elements taken from the famed legendary tales of the Cumaean Sibyl and St. Patrick's Purgatory, also marked by lakes and caves. Thus, the lore concerning the Lake and Cave set amid the Apennines was increasingly enriched with the inclusion of otherworldly elements which were typically contained in the most renowned accounts about Cumae and Lough Derg, like the 'test bridge' or the ever-slamming metal barriers.

In our present age, the establishment of any sort of connection between Cumae, Lough Derg and the Sibillini Mountain Range, though limited to a mere narrative level, might appear as a bold and basically unfounded conjecture. But this only happens because it is hard today to discern any link between the three different legendary traditions, which belong to territories that are different altogether and far from each other. And yet, the connection becomes utterly apparent not only when we confront with the literary witnesses which are available to us, but also if we are able to effectively put ourselves in the shoes of a man of the Middle Ages: at that time, the legendary tales about Cumae and the Purgatory of St. Patrick were well known to people, as the former was part of Vergil's *Aeneid*, a renowned classical literary masterwork, and the latter was included in Jacobus de Varagine's *Legenda Aurea*, a 'best seller' of its age. Thus, lakes and caves with an otherworldly character were part of an established, accepted classical and medieval lore: any further Lake and Cave featuring such a character would have immediately been put in relation with the two most famous legendary accounts, in a ceaseless and wide-reaching flow of oral narratives circulating throughout the whole of Europe across the centuries.

Certainly, the medieval readers of *Guerrino the Wretch* and *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* could not restrain themselves from thinking about the Cumaean Hades or the Irish Purgatory, as the Apennine story contained too many patent affinities with the two illustrious legendary tales. Affinities that the men of the Middle Ages could easily discern.

On the other side, even the Apennines were not totally unknown to the Irishmen of the Middle Ages, isolated as they were. In a fine thirteenth-century map of Europe contained in a precious manuscripted witness of Gerald of Wales' works *Topographia Hibernica* and *Expugnatio Hibernica* (MS 700, National Library of Ireland, Dublin) we find, in a same diagram

drawn by an Irish hand, both Ireland and the Italian Apennines, a sign of some sort of mutual awareness, at least at a basical narrative level.

So, we must consider the existence of a narrative connection between Cumae, Lough Derg and the Sibillini Mountain Range as a reasonable fact. The nature of this connection is merely narrative, as no actual, specific historical link has ever existed between the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate, on one side, and the legendary tales concerning Cumae and the Purgatory of St. Patrick, on the other. The three sites were too far from each other to develop any common, coordinated legendary framework. Their respective lores were totally independent from one another. Just an overall affinity, though patently manifest, linked the three places together: presence of a lake, presence of a cave, and the existence of a legendary physical passageway to an Otherworld, which attracted visitors, be they pilgrims or necromancers.

Fig. 145 - Ireland and the Italian Apennines in a thirteenth-century miniature contained in Gerald of Wales' *Topographia Hibernica* (manuscript no. 700, National Library of Ireland, Dublin, folium 48r)

Certainly, after decades of scientific and philological research, today we know many things about Lake Avernus and Lough Derg, with their

respective caves: we know a lot about the legendary tales which concern the Cumaean Sibyl and the Purgatory of St. Patrick.

But still we know nothing about the Lake and Cave nested amid the central Apennines, in Italy.

Why should this Apennine site have been considered as a further entryway to the Otherworld?

And, if our assumptions are all true, what sort of Otherworld was this?

All the clues seem to indicate that in this third, specific location of Europe, amid the Sibillini Mountain Range, by a Lake and a Cave, mortal beings like Aeneas, like Owein, may make an actual attempt to access a different world, normally forbidden to the living: a realm of dead souls, a kingdom which was set under the rule of non-human entities, of a divine, terrifying nature. A chthonian, subterranean Otherworld.

At Cumae, men imagined dreams of a pagan afterlife inhabited by the shades of the dead. At St. Patrick's Purgatory, men fancied a dream of a Christian Hell full of demons and excruciated souls.

But what sort of dreadful dream did men conceive at the Lake and Cave set amid the mountains of the central Apennines?

We still don't know. And yet, we are now beginning to form a conjecture which concerns the potential reason for which a Lake and a Cave set amid the Sibillini Mountain Range, in Italy, were turned by men in antiquity into a possible, legendary passageway to the Otherworld.

A passageway to some sort of demonic presence. An access that was to be unlocked by means of necromantic rituals. A point of contact with a subterranean Otherworld. A 'hot spot', a crevice drilled into the mountains to establish an appalling communication with the chthonian powers beneath. A break in the continuum of our ordinary world, not unlike the ghastly gap portrayed in 1346 by Jacopo di Mino del Pellicciaio in his fresco *The Purgatory of St. Patrick* at the convent of San Francesco al Borgo Nuovo at Todi, providing an access to a forbidden, inhuman realm.

Fig. 146 - The entryway to the Irish Otherworld, a detail from *The Purgatory of St. Patrick*, a fourteenth-century fresco painted by Jacopo di Mino del Pellicciaio (Convent of San Francesco al Borgo Nuovo, Todi, Umbria, Italy)

«Descendunt in infernum viventes»: «they descend alive into Hell», so wrote Petrus Berchorius in his fourteenth-century *Reductorium Morale*, quoting from the Book of Psalms (55:15). He was writing about the Lake of Norcia, in the Sibillini Mountain Range.

Fig. 147 - A descent into Hell, the Lake of Norcia, as taken from the *Reductorium Morale* by Petrus Berchorius (manuscript Latin 16786, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folium 301v)

So, an access to an Otherworld at the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate may have existed in an antique legendary tradition, though possibly different from the afterlives which were reputed to be accessible by men from Cumae and Lough Derg; and yet similar enough as to attract an uninterrupted flow of visitors to a remote, isolated, outlandish site for many centuries, the way it occurred at St. Patrick's Purgatory, too, though on a much significant scale.

A new supposition. A new theory. A legendary credence concerning an entryway to a mythical Otherworld in central Italy. One of a most terrific, dreadful sort. A crevice in our world, opened in the mountainous ridges - as we will see in our next and last article, still to be released - out of sheer terror. Terror for one own's life. Terror for the fate of one's family. Terror for the ruin of one's land.

With the next - and final - article on the legendary tales of the Sibillini Mountain Range, we will carry out an extraordinary, frightful journey through this new assumption.

And, in doing this, we will explore the deepest fears of human soul.

Fig. 148 - A magical sunset on the Sibillini Mountain Range

Michele Sanvico

END OF PART 2

**Please refer to Part 1
for the first section of this research paper**